

Regional model MSCE-HM of heavy metal transboundary air pollution in Europe

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**Regional Model MSCE-HM of Heavy Metal
Transboundary Air Pollution in Europe**

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INTRODUCTION

The EMEP/MSCE regional model of heavy metals airborne pollution (MSCE-HM) has been developed to meet the goals of Co-operative Programme for Monitoring and Evaluation of Long-Range Transmission of Air Pollutants in Europe (EMEP) to "... calculate transboundary fluxes, deposition and source attribution; analyse trends ..." [ECE/EB.AIR/73 "Strategy for EMEP 2000-2009"]. The main objectives of the model application impose certain requirements to the model characteristics. First of all, the model should adequately describe intrinsic physical and chemical processes governing heavy metals behaviour in the atmosphere to assess the pollution levels with acceptable accuracy. On the other hand, the model should not be too unwieldy to be able to perform long-term calculations in operational regime. And, finally, it should be flexible enough to meet the modern requirements of the environmental community.

The MSCE-HM model has been consistently developed from the first Eulerian-type version [Pekar, 1996] improving both the model itself and input information (such as meteorological parameters). Along with this the model performance has been validated in a number of comparison campaigns with other chemical transport models [Sofiev *et al.*, 1996; Gusev *et al.*, 2000; Ryaboshapko *et al.*, 2005]. Besides, the model sensitivity and uncertainty have been analyzed [Travnikov, 2000].

The current Technical Report contains detailed description of the MSCE-HM model along with the model sensitivity analysis. *Chapter 1* contains description of the computation domain and the model formulation of physical and chemical processes such as the atmospheric transport, chemical transformations and removal. A particular attention is paid to formulation of dry deposition to handle the needs of the effect-based approach with the ecosystem-dependent pollution levels.

Chapter 2 is devoted to input information required for the model calculations. Meteorological parameters, emission data, land cover information as well as data on chemical reactants concentration in the atmosphere are considered.

Results of the sensitivity analysis are presented in *Chapter 3*. The most important input parameters affecting the model output results are defined and ranged. The model uncertainty due to inaccuracy of individual parameters is evaluated and the overall uncertainty is estimated.

Chapter 1

MODEL DESCRIPTION

The EMEP/MSCE regional model of heavy metals airborne pollution (MSCE-HM) is a three-dimensional Eulerian type chemical transport model driven by off-line meteorological data. Currently the model is developed and applied for modelling such heavy metals as cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb) and mercury (Hg). Besides, pilot parameterizations for some other metals and metalloids (Cr, Ni, As) are also incorporated. This chapter contains detailed description of the model formulation. It includes definition of the computation domain, model description of the atmospheric transport, chemical transformations and removal processes. Besides, it comprises overview of initial and boundary conditions used for the modelling as well as the procedure of source-receptor relationships calculations.

1.1. Computation domain

The computation domain of the MSCE-HM model is defined on the polar stereographic projection and covers European region along with adjacent territories. The model operates in a regular grid called as the EMEP grid. Characteristics of the projection and the model grid are presented below.

Polar stereographic projection

The polar stereographic projection is a perspective projection of the Earth's surface from one of the poles (the South pole in our case) on a plane perpendicular to the Earth's axis and intersecting the surface at a fixed latitude φ_0 . The projection coordinates relates to the Earth's geographical coordinates as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x_p + R(1 + \sin \varphi_0) \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\varphi}{2}\right) \sin(\lambda - \lambda_0) \\ y &= y_p - R(1 + \sin \varphi_0) \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\varphi}{2}\right) \cos(\lambda - \lambda_0) \end{aligned} \quad (1.1)$$

where R is the Earth's radius; (x_p, y_p) are the North Pole coordinates;

λ_0 is a rotation angle (longitude parallel to the y-axes of the projection).

Ratio of a small length element on the stereographic projection to the respective element on the Earth's surface (*map factor*) is given by:

$$m = \frac{1 + \sin \varphi_0}{1 + \sin \varphi} \quad (1.2)$$

The polar stereographic projection used in the EMEP has the following parameters:

$$\varphi_0 = 60^\circ \text{ N}, \quad \lambda_0 = 32^\circ \text{ W}$$

More details on the projection characteristics can be found in [Posch *et al.*, 2001] or at the EMEP website: www.emep.int.

EMEP grid

The EMEP grid covers the area from approximately 35°W to 60°E and from the North Pole to about 20°N, and includes Europe, partly the North Atlantic and the Arctic oceans, Northern Africa, and part of Middle East (see Fig. 1.1). It has spatial resolution 50×50 km² on the projection that corresponds to the same resolution at 60°N on the Earth's surface. The actual grid size on the Earth's surface slightly decreases southward. The North Pole coordinates in the grid size units are $(x_p, y_p) = (8\Delta x, 110\Delta y)$, where $\Delta x = \Delta y = 50$ km. More detailed description of the EMEP grid is available at the *EMEP website* [www.emep.int/grid/].

Fig. 1.1. The EMEP 50×50 km² grid

Vertical structure

The vertical structure of the model is formulated in the sigma-pressure (σ - p) coordinate system [e.g. Jacobson, 1999]. The vertical σ -coordinate in this system is defined as:

$$\sigma = \frac{p - p_t}{p^*}, \quad (1.3)$$

where p is local air pressure;

p_t is pressure at the top of the model domain;

$p^* = p_s - p_t$ is difference between the ground surface and model top pressure.

The model domain consists of 15 irregular σ -layers and has a top at $p_t = 100$ hPa. The layers are confined by surfaces of constant σ do and not intersect the ground topography. The vertical grid structure of the model domain is shown schematically in Fig. 1.2. Characteristics of the σ -layers are presented in Table 1.1.

Fig. 1.2. Vertical grid structure of the model domain. The curves show boundaries of σ -layers

Table 1.1. Characteristics of the model σ -layers

Layer No.	1	2	3	4	5
Midlevel (σ)	0.995	0.985	0.97	0.945	0.91
Boundaries (σ)	1 - 0.99	0.99 - 0.98	0.98 - 0.96	0.96 - 0.93	0.93 - 0.89
Layer No.	6	7	8	9	10
Midlevel (σ)	0.87	0.825	0.75	0.65	0.55
Boundaries (σ)	0.89 - 0.85	0.85 - 0.8	0.8 - 0.7	0.7 - 0.6	0.6 - 0.5
Layer No.	11	12	13	14	15
Midlevel (σ)	0.45	0.35	0.25	0.15	0.05
Boundaries (σ)	0.5 - 0.4	0.4 - 0.3	0.3 - 0.2	0.2 - 0.1	0.1 - 0

The midlevel of the lowest σ -layer approximately corresponds to 37 m. The top of the model domain can be roughly estimated at 15 km.

1.2 Atmospheric transport

The species continuity equation describing the atmospheric transport and dispersion of a pollutant on the stereographic projection with the vertical (σ - p) coordinate has the following form:

$$-\frac{d}{dt}(qp^*) = -m^2 \nabla_H \cdot \left(qp^* \frac{\mathbf{V}_H}{m} \right) - \frac{d}{d\sigma}(qp^* \sigma) + \frac{d}{d\sigma} \left[K_z \left(\frac{g\rho}{p^*} \right)^2 \frac{d}{d\sigma}(qp^*) \right] + \sum_i S_i, \quad (1.4)$$

where $q = c/\rho$ is a species mass mixing ratio; c and ρ are the volume concentration and the local air density;

$\sigma = d\sigma/dt$ is the vertical scalar velocity in the (σ - p) coordinate;

m is the map factor;

∇_H and \mathbf{V}_H denote horizontal divergence operator and wind velocity respectively;

K_z is the vertical eddy diffusion coefficient; and g is the gravitational acceleration.

In the continuity equation we omitted horizontal eddy diffusion because of the coarse horizontal grid resolution. The local air density at fixed σ -layer is coupled with air temperature T_a and pressure difference p^* through the equation of state:

$$\rho = \frac{\sigma p^* + p_t}{R_a T_a},$$

where R_a is the gas constant for moist air.

The first two terms on the right hand side of the continuity equation describe horizontal and vertical advection of a pollutant in the atmosphere. The third term represents vertical eddy diffusion, the last term describes variety of sources and sinks (emissions, chemical transformations, depositions etc.). The equation is solved by means of the operator-splitting procedure [e.g. Yanenko, 1971; Marchuk, 1975; McRae et al., 1982]. Following this method, the original equation is approximated by several operator-split equations describing different physical and chemical processes, which are solved sequentially during each time step.

Advection

The sub-equation of the continuity equation (1.4) describing horizontal advection has the following form:

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(qp^*) = -m^2 \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(qp^* \frac{U}{m} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(qp^* \frac{V}{m} \right) \right), \quad (1.5)$$

where U and V are components of the wind velocity in x and y directions respectively.

The map factor $m = f(x, y)$ is a function of both x and y variables. In order to split the equation (1.5) into two one-dimensional equations for x and y directions, respectively, it is convenient to present it in the following form:

$$-\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\psi \hat{U}) - \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(\psi \hat{V}), \quad (1.6)$$

where new variables $\psi = qp^*/m^2$, $\hat{U} = mU$, $\hat{V} = mV$ are introduced.

Equation (1.6) is solved numerically using Bott flux-form advection scheme with fourth-order area-preserving polynomials [Bott, 1989a; 1989b, 1992]. This scheme is mass conservative, positive-definite, monotone, and is characterized by comparatively low artificial diffusion [see e.g. Dabdub and Seinfeld, 1994]. In order to reduce the time-splitting error in strong deformational flows the scheme has been modified according to [Easter, 1993].

The vertical advection part of equation (1.4) is written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(qp^*) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \sigma}(qp^* \sigma) \quad (1.7)$$

This one-dimensional advection equation is solved using the Bott scheme with second-order area-preserving polynomials generalized for a grid with variable step.

Results of basic tests of the model advection scheme are presented in Annex A.

Mass consistency

A very important issue for any air quality model is the mass consistency. It means that off-line fields of wind and surface pressure supplied by the meteorological pre-processor should satisfy the continuity equation:

$$\frac{\partial p^*}{\partial t} + m^2 \nabla_H \cdot \left(p^* \frac{V_H}{m} \right) + \frac{p^* \sigma}{\sigma} = 0. \quad (1.8)$$

In the terms of an air quality model it implies that the model maintain a uniform mass mixing ratio field of an inert tracer [Odman and Russel, 2000]. It can be exactly realized only if the air quality model and a meteorological model supplying input data have the same *discretization*, i.e. grid structure, time step, and finite-difference formulation. However, many transport models (including considered one) have the discretization different from that used in the weather prediction model (WPM) supplying the data. Besides, time resolution of the off-line meteorological data (6 hours for the model involved) is often considerably lower than the model time resolution (10-30 minutes) defined by the numerical stability of the explicit scheme. It requires temporal interpolation of the meteorological data. All mentioned above can lead to a considerable mass inconsistency and the uniform tracer field cannot be maintained. A possible approach to adjust the input meteorological fields to the model discretization is derivation of vertical wind velocity σ from the continuity equation (1.8) at each time step [Odman and Russel, 2000].

For the exact mass conservation it is important to apply to solution of equation (1.8) the same numerical scheme used for species advection description. The solution is performed in two steps:

Step 1. Solution of the horizontal constituent of the air continuity equation for p^* using Bott advection scheme

$$\frac{\partial p^*}{\partial t} = -m^2 \nabla_H \cdot \left(p^* \frac{V_H}{m} \right). \quad (1.9)$$

For the initial condition the surface pressure at the beginning of the time step $(p^*)_t$ is used. As a result a three-dimensional distribution of the intermediate pressure $(p^*)_{t+\Delta t/2} = f(x,y,\sigma)$ is obtained.

Step 2. Solution of the vertical constituent of the air continuity equation for the vertical velocity

$$\frac{\partial p^*}{\partial t} = -\frac{p^* \sigma}{\sigma}. \quad (1.10)$$

The intermediate pressure $(p^*)_{t+\Delta t/2}$ from the Step 1 is used as the initial condition; and the surface pressure at the end of the time step $(p^*)_{t+\Delta t} = f(x,y)$ interpolated from the input data is considered as a final condition. The vertical velocity is derived from equation (1.10) analytically by inversion of the Bott scheme applied for the vertical transport description.

Details of the vertical velocity calculation procedure are presented in Annex B.

Eddy diffusion

The non-linear equation for vertical eddy diffusion

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(qp^*) = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \left[K_z \left(\frac{g\rho}{p^*} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{\sigma} (qp^*) \right] \quad (1.11)$$

has been approximated by the second-order implicit numerical scheme in order to avoid restrictions of the time step caused by possible sharp gradients of the species mixing ratio. The obtained finite-difference equation is solved by means of the decomposition-backsubstitution method.

1.3 Atmospheric chemistry

Such heavy metals as lead and cadmium and their compounds are characterized by very low volatility. It is assumed in the model that these metals (as well as some others – nickel, chromium, zinc etc.) are transported in the atmosphere only in the composition of aerosol particles. It is believed that their possible chemical transformations do not change properties of their particles-carriers with regard to removal processes.

On the contrary, mercury transformations in the atmosphere include transitions between the gaseous, aqueous and solid phases, chemical reactions in the gaseous and aqueous environment. Hereafter we shall use the term “aqueous phase” for all species dissolved in cloud water and those in composition of solid particles suspended in a droplet. Besides, we shall distinguish three main mercury forms in the atmospheric air: gaseous elemental mercury (GEM), total particulate mercury (TPM) and reactive gaseous mercury (RGM). The last form mostly consists of divalent mercury compounds in gaseous phase, the most typical of which is mercury chloride ($HgCl_2$). The general scheme of mercury transformations in the atmosphere is illustrated in Fig. 1.3.

Fig. 1.3. Scheme of chemical transformations of mercury in the atmosphere

Inter-phase equilibrium

All gaseous mercury compounds are soluble to some extent in cloud- and rainwater. Size of cloud droplets is small enough to establish the equilibrium between the solution and the gas rather rapidly. The equilibrium described by Henry's law has pronounced temperature dependence. The expression for the Henry's law constants (in the form of the ratio of a species concentration in liquid to its air concentration, M·cm³/molec) are given by

$$H = A_H T \exp \left[B_H \left(\frac{T_0}{T} - 1 \right) \right], \quad (1.12)$$

where $T_0 = 298.15$ K; coefficients A_H and B_H for gaseous mercury forms and other gases of interest are presented in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2. Coefficients of Henry's law constants

Compound	A_H	B_H	Reference
Hg^0	$1.76 \cdot 10^{-23}$	9.08	Andersson et al., 2004
$HgCl_2$	$1.75 \cdot 10^{-16}$	18.75	Ryaboshapko et al., 2001
O_3	$1.58 \cdot 10^{-24}$	7.8	Sander, 1997
$\cdot OH$	$3.41 \cdot 10^{-21}$	17.72	Jacobson, 1999
Cl_2	$4.48 \cdot 10^{-16}^*$		Lin and Pehkonen, 1999

* - no temperature dependence is available

Besides, we expect that half of particulate mercury mass in cloud- and rainwater is represented by soluble compounds [Brosset and Lord, 1991; Fitzgerald et al., 1991; Lamborg et al., 1995]. On the other hand, it is assumed that all mercury mass in the aqueous phase is transformed to the particulate form if the cloud droplet is evaporated.

Gas-phase reactions

One of the most important gas phase reactions is oxidation of elemental mercury by ozone:

Since, ozone is always in plenty under ordinary atmospheric conditions this second-order reaction is described by a first-order rate expression with the reaction rate constant depending on the reactant concentration:

$$R_1 = -\frac{d[Hg_{(gas)}^0]}{dt} = k'_1[Hg_{(gas)}^0], \quad (1.14)$$

$$k'_1 = k_1[O_{3(gas)}], \quad k_1 = A \exp(-E_a / (R_{univ} T))$$

where $A = 2.1 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ cm}^3/(\text{molec} \cdot \text{s})$ [Hall, 1995];

$$E_a = 10.36 \text{ kJ/mole};$$

$$R_{univ} = 8.31 \text{ J/(mole} \cdot \text{K)};$$

$[O_{3(gas)}]$ is ozone concentration, molec/cm^3 .

It is believed that the product of the reaction – mercury oxide is in particulate form due to its poor volatility [Sommar et al., 2001; Schroeder and Munthe, 1998].

Recently investigated reaction of mercury oxidation by hydroxyl radical in gaseous phase is expected to be very significant or even prevailing sink of elemental mercury in the troposphere [Sommar et al., 1999; 2001; Pal and Ariya, 2004]:

$$R_2 = -\frac{d[Hg_{(gas)}^0]}{dt} = k'_2[Hg_{(gas)}^0], \quad k'_2 = k_2[\cdot OH_{(gas)}], \quad (1.16)$$

where $k_2 = 8.7 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ cm}^3/(\text{molec} \cdot \text{s})$ [Sommar et al., 2001];

$[\cdot OH_{(gas)}]$ is hydroxyl radical concentration, molec/cm^3 .

Gas phase oxidation of elemental mercury by chlorine can be noticeable in the ocean boundary layer during nighttime [Seigneur et al., 1994; Tokos et al., 1998; Ariya et al., 2002]:

$$R_3 = -\frac{d[Hg_{(gas)}^0]}{dt} = k_3'[Hg_{(gas)}^0], \quad k_3' = k_3[Cl_{2(gas)}], \quad (1.18)$$

where $k_3 = 2.6 \cdot 10^{-18} \text{ cm}^3/(\text{molec} \cdot \text{s})$ [Ariya et al., 2002];
 $[Cl_{2(gas)}]$ is chlorine concentration, molec/cm^3 .

Aqueous-phase reactions

Dissolved elemental mercury is oxidized by ozone producing mercury oxide HgO , which is very short-lived in the liquid phase and is rapidly transformed to the mercury ion Hg_{aq}^{2+} . Thus, the resulting reaction can be written as follows:

with the reaction rate expression:

$$R_4 = -\frac{d[Hg_{(aq)}^0]}{dt} = k_4'[Hg_{(aq)}^0], \quad k_4' = k_4 H_{O_3} [O_{3(gas)}]. \quad (1.20)$$

Here $k_4 = 4.7 \cdot 10^7 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [Munthe, 1992];
 $[O_{3(gas)}]$ is ozone concentration, molec/cm^3 ;
 H_{O_3} is Henry's constant for ozone.

Another important reaction of mercury oxidation in aqueous phase is reaction with hydroxyl radical:

Reaction rate expression for this reaction has the following form:

$$R_5 = -\frac{d[Hg_{(aq)}^0]}{dt} = k_5'[Hg_{(aq)}^0]; \quad k_5' = k_5 H_{OH} [\bullet OH_{(gas)}] \quad (1.22)$$

where $k_5 = 2.4 \cdot 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [Gårdfeldt et al., 2001];
 $[\bullet OH_{(gas)}]$ is hydroxyl radical concentration, molec/cm^3 ;
 H_{OH} is Henry's constant for hydroxyl radical.

Elemental mercury in aqueous phase is also oxidized by dissolved chlorine $Cl(l)_{aq}$ with formation of mercury ion Hg_{aq}^{2+} :

$$R_6 = -\frac{d[Hg_{(aq)}^0]}{dt} = k'_6[Hg_{(aq)}^0]; \quad k'_6 = k_6 H_{Cl_2} [Cl_{2(gas)}], \quad (1.24)$$

where $k_6 = 2 \cdot 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ [Lin and Pehkonen, 1999];
 $[Cl_{2(gas)}]$ is chlorine concentration, molec/cm³;
 H_{Cl_2} is Henry's constant for chlorine.

Mercury ion Hg_{aq}^{2+} reacts in the solution with sulphite ions SO_3^{2-} resulting in the formation of mercury sulphite complex $Hg(SO_3)_2^{2-}$ [Pleijel and Munte, 1995]:

The reaction rate is determined by the air concentration of SO_2 and the cloud water pH :

$$R_7 = -\frac{d[Hg_{(aq)}^{2+}]}{dt} = k'_7[Hg_{(aq)}^{2+}], \quad k'_7 = k_7 [SO_{2(gas)}]^2 \cdot 10^{4pH}, \quad (1.26)$$

where $k_7 = 1.1 \cdot 10^{-21} \text{ s}^{-1}$, and $[SO_{2(gas)}]$ is in ppbv.

The sulphite complex $Hg(SO_3)_2^{2-}_{(dis)}$ is dissociated to mercury sulphite $HgSO_3$, which is unstable, and is readily reduced to $Hg_{(aq)}^0$. Thus, the reduction process can be described as:

with the reaction rate expression:

$$R_8 = -\frac{d[Hg(SO_3)_2^{2-}_{(dis)}]}{dt} = k_8 [Hg(SO_3)_2^{2-}_{(dis)}], \quad (1.28)$$

where $k_8 = 4.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

This process increases the amount of dissolved elemental mercury in a droplet hampering further dissolution of gaseous mercury. Hence, the scheme implies negative feedback controlling elemental mercury uptake from the air.

Mercury ion $Hg_{(aq)}^{2+}$ also takes part in a number of reactions leading to the formation of various chloride complexes $Hg_n Cl_m$ (R_9). These reversible reactions in the first approximation can be replaced by equilibrium concentrations of free mercury ions and mercury in the aggregate of chloride complexes ($[HgCl^+]$, $[HgCl_2]$, $[HgCl_3^-]$, $[HgCl_4^{2-}]$). The equilibrium ratio of the appropriate mercury concentrations depends upon water content of chloride ion $[Cl^-]$ and is defined as follows [Lurie, 1971]:

$$r_1 = \frac{[Hg_n Cl_m]_{(dis)}}{[Hg_{(aq)}^{2+}]} = \frac{[Cl_{(aq)}^-]}{1.82 \cdot 10^{-7}} + \frac{[Cl_{(aq)}^-]^2}{6.03 \cdot 10^{-14}} + \frac{[Cl_{(aq)}^-]^3}{8.51 \cdot 10^{-15}} + \frac{[Cl_{(aq)}^-]^4}{8.51 \cdot 10^{-16}}. \quad (1.29)$$

The chloride ion concentration in cloud water is taken as $7 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ [Acker et al., 1998]. Sulphite and chloride complexes in the aqueous phase can be adsorbed and desorbed by soot particles (R_{10} , R_{11}). Comparatively fast equilibrium of these two reverse processes can also be described by means of

“dissolved-to-adsorbed ratio”. Based on the appropriate reaction rates it could be taken equal to 0.2 in both cases [Petersen *et al.*, 1998]:

$$r_2 = \frac{[Hg(SO_3)_2]_{(dis)}^{2-}}{[Hg(SO_3)_2]_{(soot)}^{2-}} = \frac{[Hg_nCl_m]_{(dis)}}{[Hg_nCl_m]_{(soot)}} \approx 0.2. \quad (1.30)$$

Summary of all chemical transformations of mercury included into the model is presented in Table 1.3.

Table 1.3. Summary of mercury transformations included into the model

Reactions and equilibriums	k or H	Units	Reference
$Hg_{(gas)}^0 + O_{3(gas)} \rightarrow Hg(II)_{(part)} + products$	$2.1 \cdot 10^{-18} \exp(-1247/T)$	$cm^3/(molec \cdot s)$	Hall, 1995
$Hg_{(gas)}^0 + \bullet OH_{(gas)} \rightarrow Hg(II)_{(part)} + products$	$8.7 \cdot 10^{-14}$	$cm^3/(molec \cdot s)$	Sommar <i>et al.</i> , 2001
$Hg_{(gas)}^0 + Cl_{2(gas)} \rightarrow Hg(II)_{(gas)}$	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-18}$	$cm^3/(molec \cdot s)$	Ariya <i>et al.</i> , 2002
$Hg_{(aq)}^0 + O_{3(aq)} \rightarrow Hg_{(aq)}^{2+} + products$	$4.7 \cdot 10^7$	$M^{-1}s^{-1}$	Munthe, 1992
$Hg_{(aq)}^0 + \bullet OH_{(aq)} \rightarrow Hg_{(aq)}^{2+} + products$	$2.4 \cdot 10^9$	$M^{-1}s^{-1}$	Gårdfeldt <i>et al.</i> , 2001
$Hg_{(aq)}^0 + Cl(I)_{(aq)} \rightarrow Hg_{(aq)}^{2+} + products$	$2 \cdot 10^6$	$M^{-1}s^{-1}$	Lin and Pehkonen, 1999
$Hg_{(aq)}^{2+} + 2SO_3^{2-} \rightarrow Hg(SO_3)_2^{2-}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-21} [SO_2]_{(gas)}^2 \cdot 10^{4pH^*}$	s^{-1}	Petersen <i>et al.</i> , 1998
$Hg(SO_3)_2^{2-} \rightarrow Hg_{(aq)}^0 + products$	$4.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$	s^{-1}	Petersen <i>et al.</i> , 1998
$Hg_nCl_m]_{(dis)} \leftrightarrow Hg_{(aq)}^{2+}$	$f([Cl])^{**}$	1	Lurie, 1971
$Hg_nCl_m]_{(dis)} \leftrightarrow Hg_nCl_m]_{(soot)}$	0.2	1	Petersen <i>et al.</i> , 1998
$Hg(SO_3)_2^{2-} (dis) \leftrightarrow Hg(SO_3)_2^{2-} (soot)$	0.2	1	Petersen <i>et al.</i> , 1998
$Hg_{(gas)}^0 \leftrightarrow Hg_{(aq)}^0$	$1.76 \cdot 10^{-23} T \exp(9.08(T_0/T-1))$	$M \cdot cm^3/molec$	Andersson <i>et al.</i> , 2004
$HgCl_{2(gas)} \leftrightarrow HgCl_{2(aq)}$	$1.75 \cdot 10^{-16} T \exp(18.75(T_0/T-1))$	$M \cdot cm^3/molec$	Ryaboshapko <i>et al.</i> , 2001
$O_{3(gas)} \leftrightarrow O_{3(aq)}$	$1.58 \cdot 10^{-24} T \exp(7.8(T_0/T-1))$	$M \cdot cm^3/molec$	Sander, 1997
$\bullet OH_{(gas)} \leftrightarrow \bullet OH_{(aq)}$	$3.41 \cdot 10^{-21} T \exp(17.72(T_0/T-1))$	$M \cdot cm^3/molec$	Jacobson, 1999
$Cl_{2(gas)} \leftrightarrow Cl(I)_{(aq)}$	$4.48 \cdot 10^{-16}$	$M \cdot cm^3/molec$	Lin and Pehkonen, 1999

* - $[SO_2]_{(gas)}$ is in ppbv

** - see Eq. (1.29)

As it was mentioned above one can distinguish three groups of mercury compounds being in equilibrium. The first group (A) contains elemental mercury in the gaseous and dissolved phase; the second one (B) consists of the mercury sulphite complex both dissolved and on soot particles; and the third group (C) includes free mercury ions, mercury chloride complexes dissolved and adsorbed by soot particles and gaseous mercury chloride:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= Hg_{(gas)}^0 + Hg_{(aq)}^0, \\ B &= Hg(SO_3)_2^{2-} (dis) + Hg(SO_3)_2^{2-} (soot), \\ C &= Hg_{(aq)}^{2+} + Hg_nCl_m]_{(dis)} + Hg_nCl_m]_{(soot)} + HgCl_{2(gas)}. \end{aligned} \quad (1.31)$$

According to this simplified scheme and introduced notations mercury transformations in the liquid phase are described by the following system of the first-order differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d[A]}{dt} = -\alpha(k'_4 + k'_5 + k'_6)[A] + \beta k_8[B], \\ \frac{d[B]}{dt} = -\beta k_8[B] + \gamma k'_7[C], \\ \frac{d[C]}{dt} = -\gamma k'_7[C] + \alpha(k'_4 + k'_5 + k'_6)[A]. \end{cases} \quad (1.32)$$

Here $\alpha = H_{Hg}C_w / (\rho_w + H_{Hg}C_w)$ is the fraction of mercury in the A group corresponding to the dissolved form; ρ_w is water density; C_w is cloud liquid water content defined as mass of cloud water per unit volume. Parameter $\beta = r_2 / (1 + r_2)$ denotes mercury fraction of the B group in the dissolved phase. Value $\gamma = r_2 r'_3 / (r_1 r_3 + r_2 r'_3 + r_1 r_2)$ is the fraction of mercury in the C group corresponding to the mercury ion Hg_{aq}^{2+} . Parameter $r_3 = H_{HgCl_2}C_w / (\rho_w + H_{HgCl_2}C_w)$ is the fraction of mercury chloride $HgCl_2$ in cloud water. The analytical solution of the equations system with appropriate initial conditions defines mercury evolution in the aqueous phase during one time step.

Mercury depletion events (MDE)

Rapid transformation of elemental mercury to divalent forms with subsequent intensive deposition has been observed in the Arctic during springtime [Schroeder *et al.*, 1998; Berg *et al.*, 2001; Lu *et al.*, 2001; Lindberg *et al.*, 2002; Ebinghaus *et al.*, 2002]. This phenomenon, which named as *Mercury Depletion Events* (MDE), could be crucial for the Arctic contamination with mercury and adverse impacts on its vulnerable ecosystems. The kinetic mechanism of the phenomenon associated with halogen-related chemistry is not clear understood yet as well as very few measurement data on the reactions kinetics are available. A simplified parameterization of the MDE phenomenon have been developed and used in the sensitivity analysis (*Chapter 3*) to assess the overall effect of the phenomenon on mercury depositions in the Arctic. The main assumptions of the parameterization are presented below:

1. We assume that MDE can occur only over open seawater areas, which were previously covered with ice during winter period. We exclude a possibility of penetration of halogen precursors through ice cover. Hence, we think that MDE can take place over coastal zones of the Arctic Ocean. Only those grid cells are taken into account, which cover both land and see.
2. We suppose that the water surface was previously covered with ice if air temperature in a given point was permanently lower than -3°C during wintertime (assumed seawater freezing point). Then in springtime the temperature became higher than 0°C , and ice melting started. Besides, during springtime ice-drift becomes more intensive and areas of open water appear. Conditionally we “switch on” the MDE module if air temperature during previous 24 hours was higher that 0°C . We understand the conventional character of such a “trigger” because open water can appear in reality at low negative temperatures.
3. We assume that total duration of MDE during springtime in any point does not exceed 4 weeks and MDE takes place every day (instantly at noon) during this period. The MDE module can be “switched on” only within the period from April to June.
4. We believe that during the MDE concentration of elemental mercury near the surface layer drops down from its usual level to 0.1 ng/m^3 . Oxidation of Hg^0 leads to the formation of RGM (50%) and Hg_{part} (50%). The oxidized products are partly scavenged from the atmosphere within a given modelling grid cell, partly transported outside it and scavenged later.

5. We accept that the MDE covers the lowest 1-kilometer height layer of the atmosphere. Within this layer the intensity of the phenomenon linearly decreases with height to zero at the top of the layer. Hence, during the MDE elemental mercury has rising profile from 0.1 ng/m^3 at the surface to its usual values at 1 km height. Contrary, oxidized forms have dropping profile from their maximum at the surface to their usual values at 1 km height.

Fig. 1.4. AMAP Arctic area [AMAP, 1998]

We applied the Arctic definition adopted in the AMAP programme (Fig. 1.4). It covers the terrestrial and marine areas north of the Arctic Circle, north of 62°N in Asia and 60°N in North America, modified to include the marine areas north of the Aleutian chain, Hudson Bay, and parts of the North Atlantic Ocean including the Labrador Sea.

1.4. Dry deposition

One of the processes accounting for removal of heavy metals from the atmosphere is dry deposition. Heavy metals in aerosol composition or in gaseous form interact with ground surface (buildings, trees, grass, soil, water surface etc.). As a result they stick or react with the surface and are removed from the air. Dry deposition of a substance to a particular surface type i is described by the equation:

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = -\Lambda_{dry}^i q, \quad (1.33)$$

where Λ_{dry}^i is the surface dependent dry deposition coefficient, proportional to dry deposition velocity V_d^i :

$$\Lambda_{dry}^i = \frac{V_d^i}{\Delta\sigma_1} \left| \frac{\partial\sigma}{\partial z} \right|, \quad \frac{\partial\sigma}{\partial z} = -\frac{g}{R_a T_a} \left(\sigma_1 + \frac{p_i}{p^*} \right). \quad (1.34)$$

Here $\Delta\sigma_1$ and σ_1 are depth and mid-level of the lowest σ -layer respectively.

The pollutant mixing ratio averaged over a gridcell after the dry deposition is given by:

$$q^{t+\Delta t} = q^t \sum_i f_i \exp(-\Lambda_{dry}^i \Delta t) \quad (1.35)$$

where f_i is area fraction of a surface type i in a gridcell and summing is performed over all surface types in the cell.

Commonly the dry deposition velocity is calculated using the resistance analogy [e.g. *Wesely and Hicks, 2000*]. For gases it has the following form:

$$V_d^i = \frac{1}{R_a + R_b + R_c}, \quad (1.36)$$

where R_a is the aerodynamic resistance between a reference height (mid-level of the lowest σ -layer) and the quasi-laminar sub-layer above the surface;

R_b is the quasi-laminar sub-layer resistance;

R_c is the surface resistance to chemical, physical and biological interactions.

Dry deposition velocities of aerosol differ from those of gases (Eq. (1.36)) by absence of the surface resistance and influence of the gravitational sedimentation [Seinfeld and Pandis, 1997]:

$$V_d^i = \frac{1}{R_a + R_b + R_a R_b V_g} + V_g, \quad (1.37)$$

where V_g is the gravitational sedimentation velocity.

Aerodynamic resistance

The aerodynamic resistance can be approximated from the similarity theory as [Jacobson, 1999]:

$$R_a = \frac{1}{k u_*} \int_{z_{0h}}^{z_{ref}-d} \Phi_h \frac{dz}{z}, \quad (1.38)$$

where k is the von Kármán constant taken as 0.4;

u_* is the friction velocity;

z_{ref} is the reference height (mid-level of the lowest σ -layer);

d is the displacement height;

z_{0h} is the energy roughness length; and Φ_h is the dimensionless potential temperature gradient.

The friction velocity is given by:

$$u_* = k U_{ref} \left(\int_{z_{0m}}^{z_{ref}-d} \Phi_m \frac{dz}{z} \right)^{-1}, \quad (1.39)$$

where U_{ref} is wind velocity at the reference height;

z_{0m} is the roughness length for momentum;

Φ_m is the dimensionless wind shear.

The momentum roughness length z_{0m} for different land cover types along with the displacement heights are given in Table 2.6 (*Chapter 2*). The roughness length for water surfaces is a function of the friction velocity [Garratt, 1999]:

$$z_{0m} = \alpha_c u_*^2 / g + 0.11 \nu / u_*, \quad (1.40)$$

where $\alpha_c \approx 0.016$ is the Charnock constant; and ν is the kinematic viscosity of air.

The energy roughness length is expressed through that of momentum for a wide variety of surfaces [Garratt, 1999]:

$$\ln\left(\frac{z_{0m}}{z_{0h}}\right) \approx \begin{cases} 2 & \text{rough surface} \\ k(13.6\text{Pr}^{2/3} - 12) & \text{water surface} \end{cases}, \quad (1.41)$$

where $\text{Pr} = \nu\rho c_{pm}/\kappa$ is the Prandtl number;

ρ is air density;

c_{pm} is the specific heat of moist air;

κ is the thermal air conductivity.

The integrals of Φ_h and Φ_m in Eqs. (1.38) and (1.39) are calculated as follows [Jacobson, 1999]:

$$\int_{z_{0h}}^z \Phi_h \frac{dz}{z} = \begin{cases} \text{Pr}_t \ln \frac{z}{z_{0h}} + \frac{\beta_h}{L} (z - z_{0h}) & z/L > 0 \quad (\text{stable}) \\ \text{Pr}_t \left[\ln \frac{(1 - \gamma_h z/L)^{1/2} - 1}{(1 - \gamma_h z/L)^{1/2} + 1} - \ln \frac{(1 - \gamma_h z_{0h}/L)^{1/2} - 1}{(1 - \gamma_h z_{0h}/L)^{1/2} + 1} \right] & z/L < 0 \quad (\text{unstable}) \\ \text{Pr}_t \ln \frac{z}{z_{0h}} & z/L = 0 \quad (\text{neutral}) \end{cases} \quad (1.42)$$

$$\int_{z_{0h}}^z \Phi_m \frac{dz}{z} = \begin{cases} \ln \frac{z}{z_{0m}} + \frac{\beta_m}{L} (z - z_{0m}) & z/L > 0 \quad (\text{stable}) \\ \ln \frac{(1 - \gamma_m z/L)^{1/4} - 1}{(1 - \gamma_m z/L)^{1/4} + 1} - \ln \frac{(1 - \gamma_m z_{0m}/L)^{1/4} - 1}{(1 - \gamma_m z_{0m}/L)^{1/4} + 1} & z/L < 0 \quad (\text{unstable}) \\ \ln \frac{z}{z_{0m}} & z/L = 0 \quad (\text{neutral}) \end{cases} \quad (1.43)$$

Here $\text{Pr}_t \approx 0.95$ is the turbulent Prandtl number;

$\beta_h = 7.8$; $\gamma_h = 11.6$; $\beta_m = 6.0$; $\gamma_m = 19.3$;

L is the Monin-Obukhov length.

Gridcell averaged values of the Monin-Obukhov length are supported by the meteorological pre-processor (see Chapter 2). To obtain values specific for each land cover type we use the following expression for L [Jacobson, 1999]:

$$L = -\frac{c_{pd}\rho\theta_v}{kgH_f} u_*^3, \quad (1.44)$$

where c_{pd} is the specific heat of dry air;

θ_v is the potential virtual temperature;

H_f is the vertical turbulent sensible-heat flux.

The Eqs. (1.39) and (1.44) are iterated for u_* and L using the cell averaged values for the initial estimate.

Aerosol deposition

Dry deposition velocities of aerosol is described by Eq. (1.37), where the gravitational sedimentation velocity V_g is given as follows:

$$V_g = \frac{d_p^2 \rho_p g}{18\eta} G_{cunn} . \quad (1.45)$$

Here d_p and ρ_p are the aerosol diameter and density respectively;

$G_{cunn} = 1 + Kn (1.249 + 0.42 \exp(-0.87 / Kn))$ is the Cunningham correction factor [Jacobson, 1999];

$Kn = 2\lambda / d_p$ is the Knudsen number; and λ is the mean free path of air molecules.

In the moist atmospheric air condensation of water vapor on aerosol particles leads to increase of their size. The diameter of an aerosol that is in equilibrium with the air moisture depends upon ambient humidity [Fitzgerald, 1975]:

$$d_p = Ad_d^B ; \quad A = 1.2 \exp\left(\frac{0.066S}{1.058 - S}\right); \quad B = \exp\left(\frac{0.00077S}{1.009 - S}\right), \quad (1.46)$$

where d_d is the dry diameter of an aerosol;

S is the air saturation ratio.

In this parameterization we expect that the water absorbing mass fraction of the aerosol is equal to unity.

Vegetated surfaces

The size-segregated approach developed for dry deposition to vegetated surfaces is based on theoretical work [Slinn, 1982] and fitted to experimental data. Empirical parameterizations based on extensive field measurements [Ruijgrok et al., 1997; Wesely et al., 1985] are used for selection of the model parameters. A similar approach is suggested by L.Zhang et al. [2001]. Following [Slinn, 1982] the deposition velocity is expressed in simplified form:

$$V_d^{veg} = \frac{1}{R_a + R_s} + V_g . \quad (1.47)$$

Here R_s is the resistance of the interfacial sub-layer (the layer within and just above the roughness elements) also called as the 'canopy resistance'.

This resistance is calculated as follows:

$$R_s = \frac{U_h}{EU_*^2}, \quad (1.48)$$

where E is the total efficiency of particles collection by the surface;

U_h is the wind velocity at the canopy height H given as:

$$U_h = \frac{u_*}{k} \int_{z_{0m}}^{H-d} \Phi_m \frac{dz}{z}. \quad (1.49)$$

Following *W.G.N.Slinn* [1982] and *L.Zhang et al.* [2001] the collection efficiency has the following form:

$$E = \varepsilon_0(E_b + E_{in} + E_{im})r_{off}, \quad (1.50)$$

where E_b , E_{in} , E_{im} are constituents of the collection efficiency from Brownian diffusion, interception and impaction respectively;

r_{off} represents reduction of the efficiency caused by particles bounce-off;

ε_0 is the empirical constant taken from fitting to the experimental data.

The diffusion term is given as [*Slinn*, 1982]:

$$E_b = Sc^{-2/3}, \quad (1.51)$$

where $Sc = \nu / D_p$ is the Schmidt number;

D_p is the particle Brownian diffusion coefficient.

We use a generalized form of the impaction term suggested in [*Peters and Eiden*, 1992]:

$$E_{im} = \left(\frac{St}{\alpha + St} \right)^\beta, \quad (1.52)$$

where $St = u_* V_g / (g\hat{A})$ is the Stokes number for vegetated surfaces;

\hat{A} is the characteristic collector width given below;

α and β are constants chosen to fit the experimental data.

The interception term is the most uncertain part of the collection efficiency. *W.G.N.Slinn* [1982] parameterized it composing contributions of small (vegetative hairs) and large (grass blades, needles etc.) collectors:

$$E_{in} = F \frac{d_p}{d_p + \check{A}} + (1-F) \frac{d_p}{d_p + \hat{A}}, \quad (1.53)$$

where \check{A} and \hat{A} are characteristics width of small and large collectors taken as 10 μm and 1 mm respectively;

F and $(1-F)$ are the contributions of these two collector types, where $F = 0.01$.

The choice of these parameters is arbitrary to some extent since there is no experimental or theoretical data on their values. However, the sensitivity analysis has shown that the interception term is insignificant in comparison with two other terms.

The bounce-off correction factor is taken in the form [*Slinn*, 1982]:

$$r_{off} = \exp(-\gamma St^\delta), \quad (1.54)$$

where γ and δ are the fitting constants.

It is assumed that the particles bounce-off takes place from dry surfaces only. The surface is supposed to be dry if no precipitation occurred during current 6-hours meteorological period for grass and during current and previous periods for forest.

Forests

To evaluate the constants of the deposition scheme described above for tall vegetation (forests) the scheme was fitted to empirical parameterization developed by *W.Ruijgrok et al.* [1997]. This parameterization is based on extensive measurements of dry deposition velocities of aerosol particles over needleleaf and some mixed forests. It takes into account dependence of the dry deposition velocity on the friction velocity and relative humidity of the ambient air. Particles of two size ranges are described: fine fraction with mass median diameter (MMD) = 0.6 μm (NH_4 , SO_4 , NO_3) and coarse fraction with MMD = 5.12 μm (Na). Parameters of dry deposition of different particles in the fine fraction vary insignificantly therefore mean values of the coefficients were used. The fitting constants of the dry deposition scheme obtained for forests are presented in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4. Empirical constants of the dry deposition scheme for vegetated surfaces

Constant	Forests	Low vegetation
α	1	1
β	0.5	0.5
γ	2	2
δ	0.25	0.25
ε_0	1.4	0.22
A	–	100

A comparison of the collection efficiency of the Ruijgrok's parameterization with the model scheme is shown in Figs. 1.5 and 1.6 for particles with $d_p = 0.6 \mu\text{m}$ over a wet surface. As seen both schemes give similar functional dependencies on the ambient air relative humidity and the friction velocity. The model scheme predicts more intensive increase of the collection efficiency for relative humidity close to 100%. Similar results are also obtained for a dry surface and for particles with $d_p = 5.12 \mu\text{m}$.

Fig.1.5. Collection efficiency over forest (wet surface) as a function of the ambient air relative humidity

Fig. 1.6. Collection efficiency over forest (wet surface) as a function of the friction velocity

Figs. 1.7 and 1.8 shows the dry deposition velocity of aerosol particles over wet and dry forest surface respectively as a function of a particle size. The solid line presents the model scheme, filled squares show the Ruijgrok's parameterization for particles with MMD 0.6 μm and 5.12 μm . As seen from the figures both schemes are in good agreement. The dry deposition velocity of coarse particles over a dry surface is somewhat lower than that over a wet surface because of the bounce-off effect. Besides,

the model scheme was tested using the full set of meteorological data. Fig. 1.9 shows the cumulative distribution function of dry deposition velocity over coniferous forests in Europe obtained for the year 2000 by the model scheme and the Ruijgrok's parameterization. As seen from the figure the results practically coincide.

Fig. 1.7. Dry deposition velocity to forest (wet surface) as a function of a particle size. Solid lines show the model results, the filled squares depict the Ruijgrok's parameterization

Fig. 1.8. Dry deposition velocity to forest (dry surface) as a function of particle size. Solid lines show the model results, the filled squares depict the Ruijgrok's parameterization

Fig. 1.9. Cumulative distribution function of dry deposition velocity over coniferous forests in Europe

Low vegetation

For low vegetation (grassland, crops, wetland etc.) a procedure similar to that described above was used to evaluate the constants of the dry deposition scheme. The scheme was fitted to the empirical parameterization developed from field measurements of particles dry deposition to grass [Wesely *et al.*, 1985]. The expression for the interfacial sub-layer resistance (1.48) was modified to take into account the atmospheric stability conditions as suggested by M.L. Wesely *et al.* [1985]:

$$R_s = \begin{cases} \frac{U_h}{Eu_*^2} & L \geq 0 \\ \frac{U_h}{Eu_*^2} \left[1 + \left(-\frac{A}{L} \right)^{2/3} \right]^{-1} & L < 0 \end{cases}, \quad (1.55)$$

where A is a fitting constant.

Values of the fitting constants of the model dry deposition scheme for low vegetation are presented in Table 1.4. Fig. 1.10 shows the comparison of the model scheme for grass with the Wesely's parameterization. As seen the interfacial sub-layer conductivity (reciprocal resistance) given by the Wesely's parameterization lies between those predicted by the model for dry and wet surfaces. The

dry deposition velocity over grass (dry surface) as a function of a particle size is illustrated in Fig. 1.11. The cumulative distribution function of dry deposition velocity over grassland in Europe for conditions of 2000 is shown in Fig. 1.12. As seen from the figure the model somewhat underestimates the Wesely's parameterization for small deposition velocities.

Fig. 1.10. Reciprocal resistance of the interfacial sub-layer over grass as a function of the stability conditions

Fig. 1.11. Dry deposition velocity to grass (dry surface) as a function of particle size. Solid lines show the model results, the filled squares depict the Ruijgrok's parameterization

Fig. 1.12. Cumulative distribution function of dry deposition velocity over grassland in Europe

Low vegetation covered with snow is considered as non-vegetated surface.

Water surface

The parameterization of dry deposition to water surfaces is based on the approach suggested by *R.M. Williams* [1982] taking into account the effects of wave breaking and aerosol washout by seawater spray. A similar approach was developed in [*Pryor et al.*, 1999]. The modified resistance scheme of aerosol particles dry deposition over water surface is illustrated in Fig. 1.13. Following the procedure from [*Williams*, 1982] one can obtain an expression for the dry deposition velocity:

Fig. 1.13. Resistance scheme of aerosol particles dry deposition over water surface

$$V_d^{water} = \frac{(1 + R_a V_g)(1 + R_b V_{gh})}{R_a + R_b + R_a R_b V_{gh}}, \quad (1.56)$$

where V_{gh} is the gravitational sedimentation velocity in the humid quasi-laminar layer near the air-water interface.

The relative air humidity of this layer can be significantly higher than that of the turbulent layer. It results in more intensive particle growth. Since due to Raoult's law the relative humidity over salt water cannot exceed 98.3%, the constant value of 98% is accepted in the model for the humid layer. The quasi-laminar layer resistance R_b consists of the resistance over the smooth surface R'_b and the resistance over the broken one R''_b :

$$R_b = \left(\frac{1 - \alpha_b}{R'_b} + \frac{\alpha_b}{R''_b} \right). \quad (1.57)$$

Here α_b is the fraction surface area broken due to the wind force [Wu, 1979]:

$$\alpha_b = 1.7 \cdot 10^{-6} U_{10}^{3.75}, \quad (1.58)$$

where U_{10} is the wind speed at 10 m height.

The quasi-laminar layer resistance over the smooth surface is determined mostly by the Brownian diffusion and impaction [Slinn and Slinn, 1980]:

$$R'_b = \frac{k U_{ref}}{u_*^2} (E_b + E_{im})^{-1}, \quad E_b = Sc^{-1/2}, \quad E_{im} = 10^{-3/St}, \quad (1.59)$$

where the Stokes number for water surfaces is $St = u_*^2 V_{gh} / (g \nu)$;

the Schmidt number is $Sc = \nu / D_{ph}$, D_{ph} is the diffusion coefficient in the humid layer.

The broken surface resistance R''_b governed by scavenging of particles due to impaction and coagulation with spray droplets is expected to be quite low. Because of lack of reliable estimates for this resistance a tentative value of 10 s/m [Williams, 1982] is used. Fig. 1.14 illustrates the velocity of dry deposition to water surface as a function of particle size for different values of wind speed. The influence of the broken surface resistance on the dry deposition velocity over water surfaces is illustrated in Fig. 1.15. The lowest case corresponds to water surface with no broken area.

Dry deposition to water surface covered with ice is described by the parameterization for barren land presented in the next section.

Fig. 1.14. Dry deposition velocity to water surface as a function of particle size for different values of wind speeds

Fig. 1.15. Dry deposition velocity to water surface as a function of particle size for different values of the broken surface resistance

Non-vegetated surfaces

The dry deposition to non-vegetated surfaces (deserts, glaciers etc.) is described by Equation (1.37), where the resistance of the quasi-laminar layer has the following form:

$$R_b = \frac{kU_{ref}}{u_*^2} (E_b + E_{im})^{-1}, \quad E_b = Sc^{-2/3}, \quad E_{im} = 10^{-3/St}. \quad (1.60)$$

The Schmidt and the Stokes numbers are $Sc = \nu/D_p$ and $St = u_*^2 V_g / (g\nu)$ respectively. The particular case of non-vegetated surfaces is urban area characterized by bluff roughness elements. For urban areas we used a different form of the impaction term $E_{im} = St^2 / (400 + St^2)$ [Giorgi, 1986].

Fig. 1.16 shows dry deposition velocities of particles with $d_p = 0.6 \mu\text{m}$ to different land cover categories in the EMEP region calculated for meteorological conditions of 2000. As seen the highest deposition velocities correspond to forests (around 1 cm/s), whereas the lowest – to barren land and permanent ice areas (glaciers) (below 0.01 cm/s on average).

Fig. 1.16. Dry deposition velocities of particles ($d_p = 0.6 \mu\text{m}$) to different land cover categories in the EMEP region. Bars show median values of 6-hour averages during 2000. Error bars depict 90%-confidence intervals over the model domain

The current version of the model describes particles carrying heavy metal as mono-disperse fraction with appropriate MMD: Pb – 0.55 μm , Cd – 0.84 μm , Hg – 0.61 μm [Milford and Davidson, 1985].

Reactive gaseous mercury deposition

The dry deposition of reactive gaseous mercury (RGM) is described by Eq. (1.36). The quasi-laminar resistance is given as follows [Erisman et al., 1994]:

$$R_b = \frac{2}{ku_*} \left(\frac{Sc}{Pr} \right)^{2/3}, \quad (1.61)$$

where Schmidt number $Sc = \nu/D_g$;

D_g is the molecular diffusion coefficient of RGM.

Since solubility of RGM is similar to those of nitric acid vapor [Petersen *et al.*, 1995] the surface resistance R_c is taken to be zero [Wesely and Hicks, 2000].

Dry deposition velocities of RGM to different land cover categories in the EMEP region calculated for meteorological conditions of 2000 are shown in Fig. 1.17. The highest deposition velocities are to forests and urban areas (3 cm/s on average), the lowest velocities are to inland waters (0.5 cm/s).

Fig. 1.17. Dry deposition velocities RGM to different land cover categories in the EMEP region. Bars show median values of 6-hour averages during 2000. Error bars depict 90%-confidence intervals

Gaseous elemental mercury deposition

Dry deposition of elemental gaseous mercury by various types of underlying surface is not adequately defined yet. Some experts [US EPA, 1997] suppose that this type of mercury removal is not an essential sink on a regional and global scale. According to another viewpoint [Lin and Pehkonen, 1999] dry uptake of elemental mercury is considered to be the dominating mechanism of mercury removal from the atmosphere. Summarizing available literature data [Travnikov and Ryaboshapko, 2002] we adopt the following simplified parameterization of the process. There is no dry uptake of elemental gaseous mercury by water surface and land surface not covered by vegetation. It is also absent during nighttime. Over the vegetated surface during daytime dry deposition velocity is given by:

$$V_d^{veg} = \begin{cases} 0, & T_s \leq T_0 \\ B \frac{T_s - T_0}{T_1 - T_0} \cos \theta_s, & T_0 < T_s \leq T_1 \\ B \cos \theta_s, & T_s > T_1 \end{cases}, \quad (1.62)$$

where T_s is the surface temperature, $T_0 = 273\text{K}$ and $T_1 = 293\text{K}$;

B is equal to 0.03 cm/s for forests and 0.01 cm/s for low vegetation;

θ_s is the solar zenith angle calculated according to [Jacobson, 1999].

Fog deposition

Mercury aqueous forms in fog droplets can be removed from the atmosphere through the fog interaction with the ground surface. The fog dry deposition is described in the model similar to that of aerosol particles with mass median diameter 20 μm .

1.5. Wet deposition

Another important process accounting for heavy metal removal from the atmosphere is wet deposition. Particle-bound heavy metals as well as soluble gaseous species are scavenged from the atmospheric air both in cloud environment and below the cloud base. Wet deposition of a substance is described by the equation:

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = -\Lambda_{wet}q, \quad (1.63)$$

where Λ_{wet} is the wet deposition coefficient depending on the local precipitation rate R_p .

We used the following expression for the wet deposition coefficient based on measurement data:

$$\Lambda_{wet} = A \left(\frac{R_p}{F} \right)^B. \quad (1.64)$$

Here A and B are empirical constants;

F is a fraction of the grid cell where precipitation occurs.

We adopt $F = 0.3$ for convective precipitation and $F = 1$ for stratiform one following the discussion in [Walton *et al.*, 1988]. The pollutant mixing ratio averaged over a grid cell after the wet deposition is given by:

$$q^{t+\Delta t} = q^t [1 - F(1 - \exp(-\Lambda_{wet}\Delta t))] \quad (1.65)$$

The model distinguishes in-cloud scavenging (ICS) and below-cloud scavenging (BCS).

In-cloud scavenging

In the cloud environment soluble gases dissolve very quickly in the cloud water coming into the equilibrium with the solution, while aerosol particles are taken up by cloud droplets due to nucleation or impaction scavenging. Further collection of cloud drops by falling raindrops leads to removal of the pollutants from the atmosphere. The efficiency of aerosol scavenging by cloud droplets depends upon the cloud liquid water content (LWC). Fig. 1.18 shows the scavenging efficiencies (i.e. the ratio of aerosol concentration in cloud water to its concentration in interstitial air) for Pb and SO_4 measured by A.Kasper *et al.* [1998] as a function of the LWC. For values of the LWC higher than 0.5 g/m^3 the efficiency commonly exceeds 0.8 and it drops down when the LWC become lower 0.1 g/m^3 . For the approximation of the dependence we used the following expression:

$$\varepsilon_w = \frac{C_w}{C_w + \varepsilon_{w0}}, \quad (1.66)$$

where the liquid water content C_w is in g/m^3 ;

constant ε_{w0} is equal to 0.1.

Thus for the in-cloud scavenging Eq. (1.65) is transformed to:

$$q^{t+\Delta t} = q^t [1 - \varepsilon_w F(1 - \exp(-\Lambda_{wet} \Delta t))], \quad (1.67)$$

where the scavenging efficiency ε_w for aerosol particles is defined by Eq. (1.66) and $\varepsilon_w = 1$ for aqueous forms.

Fig. 1.18. Efficiency of aerosol scavenging by cloud droplets for lead and sulfate as a function of cloud LWC. Symbols show measurement data from [Kasper et al., 1998], solid line – approximation

Parameters of the wet deposition coefficient expression (1.64) for in-cloud scavenging estimated or measured by different authors are presented in Table 1.6. Taking into account values in the table and sensitivity calculations we adopted the parameters: $A_{in} = 3 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $B_{in} = 0.8$ for all heavy metal species incorporated into cloud water.

Table 1.6. Parameters of the wet deposition coefficient for in-cloud scavenging (A_{in} is in units of s^{-1} ; R_p is in units of mm/h)

Reference	$A_{in} (\times 10^{-4})$	B_{in}	Method
Scott, 1982	3.5	0.78	Calculation
Penner et al., 1991	1.31	1	Estimation *
Brandt et al., 2002	3.36	0.79	Estimation
Andrinache, 2004	3.97	0.81	Measurement **

* ICS plus BCS of HNO_3

** Calculations based on measured ICS plus BCS

Below-cloud scavenging

Below the cloud base aerosol particles and soluble gases are collected by falling raindrops and removed from the air. The model parameterization of below-cloud scavenging is mostly based on empirical estimates. Table 1.5 presents parameters of the wet deposition coefficient for BCS of particles and highly soluble gases based on measurement data. As seen different estimates of A_{below} varies roughly from $0.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ to $2.5 \cdot 10^{-4} s^{-1}$; and B_{below} is within the range 0.62-0.79. There is no principal difference between values of the parameters for sub-micron aerosol particles and highly soluble gases. Basing on the data from the table and the sensitivity runs we adopted the values $A_{below} = 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $B_{below} = 0.7$ both particle-bound heavy metals and highly soluble gaseous species (RGM).

Table 1.5. Parameters of the wet deposition coefficient for below-cloud scavenging (A_{below} is in units of s^{-1} ; R_p is in units of mm/h)

Reference	$A_{\text{below}} (\times 10^{-4})$	B_{below}	Method
Ragland and Wilkening, 1983	1.22	0.63	Estimation
Barries, 1985	1	0.67	Measurement
Jylhä, 1991	1	0.64	Measurement
Asman, 1995	0.52-0.99	0.62	Calculation *
Okita et al., 1996	1.38	0.74	Measurement
Brandt et al., 2002	0.84	0.79	Estimation
Andrinache, 2003	0.67 – 2.44	0.7	Calculation **

* - for highly soluble gases

** - theoretical calculations based on measured aerosol size spectra

1.6. Boundary and initial conditions

Modelling of heavy metal airborne pollution requires setting appropriate boundary condition at lateral and upper boundaries of the computation domain. These conditions are aimed at taking into account influence of emission sources located outside the domain. It is particularly important for mercury because of long residence time of this pollutant in the atmosphere. Besides, one-year calculations of mean annual concentrations and deposition fluxes of the pollutant need the model domain to be filled up with the pollutant mass at the start of the modelling. Therefore, one should set some initial concentrations of the pollutant in the atmosphere before the modelling process.

Mercury

Contribution of the intercontinental transport to deposition of mercury in Europe is comparable (up to 40%) with contribution of regional sources [Ilyin et al., 2003]. Therefore, setting the proper boundary concentrations of mercury species at the domain boundaries is principally important for assessment of realistic pollution levels. Besides, it was demonstrated in the sensitivity analysis (Chapter 3) that boundary conditions are among the most important parameters determining results of mercury modelling. Available measurement data are too sparse to supply concentrations of mercury along the whole model boundary. To set the boundary conditions adequately we use modelling results obtained with the hemispheric model MSCE-HM-Hem [Travnikov and Ryaboshapko, 2002]. Main characteristics of the model are presented in Annex C. Both models have similar vertical structures, advection schemes and the same scheme of chemical transformations. Monthly mean concentrations of three atmospheric mercury forms – GEM, TPM, RGM – calculated at the EMEP domain boundaries are used as the regional model boundary conditions. Fig. 1.20 illustrates distribution of gaseous elemental mercury concentration in the vicinity of the model boundary.

Fig. 1.20. Distribution of gaseous elemental mercury in the Northern Hemisphere. Rectangular shows the EMEP domain

As it was demonstrated in aircraft measurements [e.g. *Banic et al.*, 1999] there is no pronounced gradient of GEM up to the upper troposphere. Besides, numerous measurements carried out for last decades [e.g. *Ebinghaus et al.*, 1999] have shown that elemental mercury is more or less uniformly distributed over the Northern Hemisphere. Therefore, we prescribed constant value of GEM concentration at the upper boundary – 0.185 pptv (corresponding to about 1.5 ng/m³ at 1 atm and 20°C).

Lead

Boundary conditions for lead and cadmium modelling are not so important for the central part of the EMEP region as for mercury because of significantly shorter residence time of these pollutants in the atmosphere. However, background concentrations described by the boundary conditions can have some effect on areas located not far from the model boundaries.

Hemispheric modelling of lead and cadmium airborne transport is not feasible because of lack of up-to-date emission data at the hemispheric or global scale. That is why prescribed boundary concentrations are used for these metals. Measured background concentrations of lead and cadmium in the ambient air vary mostly within the intervals 0.3-3 and 0.02-0.1 ng/m³, respectively [*Ryaboshapko et al.*, 1999; *Kriews and Schrems*, 1998; *Vinogradova*, 2002; *Aas and Breivik*, 2004]. For example, lead concentrations in the northern and northwestern part of the EMEP domain corresponding to the Arctic and the Atlantic Ocean are low because of lack of emission sources nearby (0.3-0.6 ng/m³). On the other hand, eastern boundary of the model domain lies along the Ural Mountains region, which is characterized by heavy industry and significant emissions and, therefore, relatively high the pollutants concentrations (3.5 ng/m³ and more).

On the base of measurements data the prescribed values of lead and cadmium boundary concentrations were set at several points of the model boundary (see Fig. 1.21 and Table 1.7). A linear interpolation is applied between the points with different concentration values.

Fig. 1.21. Scheme of lead and cadmium boundary concentration distribution

Table 1.7. Values of the prescribed boundary concentrations

Boundary points	Concentration, ng/m ³	
	Pb	Cd
A, B, H	0.6	0.02
C	1.5	0.04
D	3.0	0.05
E	2.0	0.05
F, G	1.0	0.03

Besides, when analysing data on air concentrations of lead and cadmium at polar stations Zeppelin (NO42) and Nord (DK10) for many years, distinct seasonal variations were found (Fig. 1.22, 1.23). Since there are no known pollution sources nearby, which can lead to such seasonal variations, the most probably they are caused by the atmospheric transport. In order to take into account this effect, the seasonal variations of boundary concentrations at the northern corner of EMEP domain (intervals AB and AH) were introduced.

Fig. 1.22. Seasonal variation of lead at monitoring stations Zeppelin (NO42) and Nord (DK10) averaged over 1994-2002

Fig. 1.23. Seasonal variation of cadmium at monitoring station Zeppelin (NO42) averaged over 1994-2002

In order to obtain vertical distribution of the boundary concentrations auxiliary model runs for lead and cadmium were performed without any boundary conditions, and average vertical profile for the appropriate region was obtained. Then a factor of the pollutant concentration decrease in comparison with the surface one was calculated for each model layer aloft. The concentration of lead and cadmium at the upper boundary is set to zero.

To fill up the model domain with mass of lead, cadmium and mercury and to achieve the initial concentrations a one-month spin up is performed for the preceding month with the same emissions values and boundary conditions.

1.7. Source-receptor relationships

For the evaluation of source-receptor relationships heavy metal mass emitted from each source (country) is considered separately. To reduce amount of computations and to avoid uncertainties connected with the model non-linearity the computation procedure is organized in such way that all model processes (advection, diffusion, chemistry, deposition etc.) deal with total mass of the pollutant not distinguishing between different sources. Instead, contribution of each source in a gridcell is stored and recalculated after each process modelling. For example, at some time step the contribution of a i^{th} source to the total pollutant mass m in a gridcell is α_i . Then the mass m is changed by value δm_1 due to a process (e.g. advection from the adjacent gridcell) with the fraction of the i^{th} source β_i . The contribution of the i^{th} source to the total pollutant mass in the gridcell ($m + \delta m_1$) at the next time step is given by:

$$\alpha'_i = \frac{\alpha_i m + \beta_i \delta m_1}{m + \delta m_1} \quad (1.68)$$

On the other hand, mass removed from a gridcell (e.g. due to dry deposition) related to the i^{th} source is calculated as $\alpha_i \delta m_2$, where δm_2 is the total pollutant mass removed from the gridcell. It should be noted that removal processes decrease the total mass in a gridcell not leading to change in contributions of different sources.

Mass entering the model domain through the boundaries is considered as originated from a separate source to take into account influence of external emission sources.

Chapter 2

INPUT INFORMATION

The MSCE-HM model operation requires various input information among which meteorological parameters, emissions data, land cover information and concentrations of different reactants are the most important. This chapter is devoted to description of these types of the model input data.

2.1. Meteorological data

Meteorological data is one of key input parameters when modelling long-range transport and deposition of atmospheric pollutants. Quality of the modelled concentrations and depositions is determined to a large extent by quality of the meteorological data. Modelling of heavy metals requires large set of meteorological parameters. Calculation of advection needs data on wind components at different altitudes of the troposphere. Description of wet removal processes requires data on three-dimensional precipitation rates. Dry deposition parameterisation uses a number of parameters of the atmospheric boundary layer (e.g. friction velocity, Monin-Obukhov length etc.). Most of the parameters are not available from the routine synoptic or aerological observations. Moreover, observation stations are randomly distributed over surface, whereas the modelling needs data on a regular grid. Therefore, it is necessary to use a pre-processing system, which can prepare gridded meteorological parameters with certain temporal resolution.

The MSCE-HM model is meant for utilizing off-line meteorological information. This means that meteorological data are not generated in the process of calculations, but periodically supplied into the model as input data. Therefore, meteorological data have to be prepared in advance and stored in the same model grid as used in the transport model. Direct interpolation of meteorological parameters to the model grid is not a proper way because it can significantly disturb the mass conservation. Besides, some parameters (e.g. atmospheric precipitation) cannot be correctly interpolated in principal. Hence, in order to provide MSCE-HM model with meteorological data a pre-processing system has been developed based on the PSU/NCAR mesoscale model MM5 [Grell *et al.*, 1995; <http://www.mmm.ucar.edu/mm5/overview.html>]. The system utilizes input meteorological data with rough spatial and temporal resolution and performs short-term weather forecast for the transport model grid.

There are several useful features of this system:

- This system can work with different sets of initial meteorological data (NCEP/DOE and ECMWF re-analyses etc.)
- Various parameterisations of physical processes (atmospheric boundary layer, precipitation, radiation transfer etc.) are available.
- This system allows operations in different map projections. In particular, the polar stereographic projection is supported.

- Nesting is available in this system. A user can perform calculations both on regional and local scales on the base of the same data assimilation system.
- The MM5 community model is spread worldwide and tested for various geographical and climatic regions. Besides, the model improvement and development are going on.
- This system can be deployed on a personal computer and can provide simulations of meteorological data for reasonable time.

In the current version of MM5 applied in the pre-processor the atmospheric boundary layer characteristics are parameterized using the *S.-Y.Hong and H.-L.Pan* [1996] scheme. Microphysics of stratiform clouds and precipitation is described according to [*Reisner et al.*, 1998]. The improved Kain-Fritsch scheme [*Kain*, 2002] is used for convective cloudiness parameterization. Besides, the radiation scheme considers interactions of short-wave and long-wave radiation with clouds and cloud-free air and predicts near-surface radiation fluxes. The MM5 forecast domain is larger than the EMEP one by 6 gridcells in each direction to reduce the effects of the lateral boundary conditions.

The following procedure is applied to prepare meteorological data for the transport model. The MM5 reads meteorological data of the objective analysis, interpolates them into EMEP grid performing the four-dimensional data assimilation (FDDA). The aim of FDDA is nudging the forecast to the data of meteorological observations or the objective analysis. Currently we use NCEP/DOE reanalysis data (dataset II) [<http://dss.ucar.edu/catalogs/ranges/range090.html>] as input information for MM5. More details about the nudging and the FDDA can be found in the MM5 technical documentation [*Grell et al.*, 1995]. After the nudging for 6-hours period the meteorological forecast takes place for the further 6-hours. The forecast output is used as input data for the transport model. The pre-processor supplies meteorological parameters with 6-hours temporal resolution. Up to date, meteorological data have been prepared for the period 1990–2003. The set of meteorological data provided by the pre-processor and short description of their usage in the model are summarised in Table 2.1. It should be noted that the vertical component of wind velocity supplied by the pre-processor is not used in the transport model to keep the mass conservation of a pollutant. Instead, the vertical velocity is calculated at each the model timestep from the continuity equation using the procedure described in Chapter 1.

Table 2.1. Meteorological parameters and their usage in the MSCE-HM model

Parameter	Notation	Dimension	Usage
Surface pressure	p_s	2D	Air density, atmospheric transport
Components of wind velocity	U, V	3D	Atmospheric transport
Air temperature	T_a	3D	Air density, atmospheric chemistry, dry deposition
Water vapour mixing ratio	q_v	3D	Air density, dry deposition
Liquid water mixing ratio	q_w	3D	Atmospheric chemistry, in-cloud scavenging
Ice mixing ratio	q_i	3D	In-cloud scavenging
Stratiform precipitation	R_s	3D	Wet removal
Convective precipitation	R_c	3D	Wet removal
Eddy diffusion coefficient	K_z	3D	Vertical eddy diffusion
Monin-Obukhov length *	L	2D	Stability, dry deposition
Surface temperature	T_s	2D	Natural emission and re-emission
Snow cover height	H_s	2D	Natural emission and re-emission

* - average over a grid cell

2.1. Emission data

Emission data are probably the most important input parameter to a great extent determining results of the modelling. Therefore, reliable values of emission at the model input are vital for realistic pollution levels at the output. Emissions of most heavy metals to the atmosphere include direct anthropogenic component, re-emission of previously deposited mass and emission from natural sources.

Anthropogenic emissions

MSCE-HM model uses for regular calculations gridded anthropogenic emissions data based both on national information officially submitted by the Parties to the Convention and expert estimates. For example, national data on heavy metal emissions for 2002 were submitted by 27 countries. For countries that have not submitted national data, a linear interpolation from previous years or expert estimates [Berdowski *et al.*, 1998; ESQUAD, 1994; Pacyna *et al.*, 2001] used in the modelling. National information on the spatial distribution of emission sources at least for one year since 1990 was submitted by 18 countries. For the rest of them expert estimates [Berdowski *et al.*, 1997] were used to distribute the total national emission over a country.

Emission distribution with height

Vertical distribution of the pollutant concentration in the vicinity of emission sources as well as long-range atmospheric transport to some extent depend on height of the emission source. For example, emissions from road transport take place near surface, whereas stacks of power stations can be as high as 1-2 hundred meters. Besides, thermal or dynamical effects can lead to significant lifting up the emissions in the atmosphere. In order to estimate distribution of emissions with height we utilized sector-split emission information provided by 20 countries. Height distributions for different emission sectors were averaged taking into account a sector contribution to the total emission. It was assumed that heavy metal emission is distributed between three lowest model layers. The dynamical lifting up of the emitted mass is not currently taken into account. The resulting distribution of lead, cadmium and mercury emissions over three lowest layers is presented in Table 2.2 (based on data for 2000).

Table 2.2. Heavy metal emission distribution with height

Model layer	Layer boundaries (m)	Emission fraction (%)		
		Pb	Cd	Hg
1	0 – 70	61	40	37
2	70 – 150	28	43	38
3	150 – 300	11	17	25

Temporal variation

Anthropogenic emissions of heavy metals have a noticeable temporal cycle (daily, seasonal etc.). Production of heat and, hence, emissions from this sector results in emission increase in winter season. Emissions from road transport sector and from electric power production have minimum at night. Seasonal variation of the emissions is taken into account in the model. The average seasonal

emission amplitudes have been calculated based on multi-years emissions data [Ryaboshapko et al., 1999]: 9% with maximum in summer for lead; 8% and 11% with maximum in winter for cadmium and mercury, respectively. It is clear, that emission variations with season can vary not only from country to country, but also in different parts of a big country. However, at present these amplitudes are applied for the whole domain.

Physical-chemical forms of heavy metal emissions

Lead, cadmium and some other heavy metals (nickel, chromium, zinc etc.) and their compounds are characterized by very low volatility. Therefore, it is assumed that they are emitted to the atmosphere in the composition of aerosol particles. In contrast to lead and cadmium, mercury can be emitted both in gaseous and in particulate forms. Besides, gaseous species include elemental and oxidized forms. The speciation of mercury emissions commonly is not included in the information submitted by the Parties to the Convention. Therefore, expert estimates of the mercury emission speciation are used in the model [Axenfeld et al., 1991; Pacyna and Münch, 1991]. Table 2.3 shows the aggregated data on speciation of mercury emissions in European countries.

Table 2.3. The ratio of individual mercury forms in direct anthropogenic emissions in various European countries [Axenfeld et al., 1991]

Country	Emission fraction (%)			Country	Emission fraction (%)		
	Hg ⁰	Hg ^{II} _{gas}	Hg ^{II} _{part}		Hg ⁰	Hg ^{II} _{gas}	Hg ^{II} _{part}
Albania	50	30	20	Kazakhstan*	51	29	20
Armenia*	51	29	20	Latvia*	51	29	20
Austria	58	25	17	Lithuania*	51	29	20
Azerbaijan*	51	29	20	Luxembourg	51	29	20
Belarus*	51	29	20	Netherlands	36	47	17
Belgium	60	25	15	Norway	69	23	8
Bosnia&Herzegovina*	56	27	17	Poland	52	29	19
Bulgaria	55	27	18	Portugal	63	30	7
Croatia*	56	27	17	Rep. of Moldova*	51	29	20
Cyprus**	51	29	20	Monaco***	51	30	19
Czech Republic*	52	30	18	Romania	50	30	20
Denmark	44	40	16	Russia*	51	29	20
Estonia*	51	29	20	Serbia and Montenegro *	56	27	17
Finland	74	18	8	Slovakia*	52	30	18
France	51	30	19	Slovenia*	56	27	17
Georgia*	51	29	20	Spain	64	26	10
Germany	60	31	9	Sweden	74	19	7
Greece	51	29	20	Switzerland	55	27	18
Hungary	52	29	19	Macedonia*	56	27	17
Island	100	0	0	Turkey**			
Ireland	50	30	20	Ukraine*	51	29	20
Italy	62	29	9	United Kingdom	52	34	14

* - The speciation is taken based on data for the former USSR, Yugoslavia and Czechoslovakia.

** - The speciation is assumed to be equal to that of Greece.

*** - The speciation is assumed to be equal to that of France

Natural emission and re-emission

Apart from anthropogenic emissions, heavy metals are emitted to the atmosphere from natural sources and due to re-emission of previously deposited substances.

Mercury

Natural emission and re-emission processes are particularly important for the mercury cycle in the environment. To take into account natural emission of mercury we used global estimates by *C.H.Lamborg et al.* [2002]. According to this work global natural emission of mercury is estimated as much as 1000 t/y from land and 800 t/y from the ocean. Review of mercury natural emission estimates and approaches to parameterization of this process can be found in [*Travnikov and Ryaboshapko*, 2002; *Ilyin et al.*, 2002].

Spatial distribution of natural emission fluxes over land was obtained by scattering the total value throughout the globe depending on mercury content in soils and the surface temperature. From this point of view four surface types were distinguished: (1) glaciers, (2) background soils, (3) soil of the geochemical mercuriferous belts, and (4) soil of mercury deposit areas. No mercury emissions are expected from glaciers. Temperature dependence on mercury emission flux from soil can be described by an Arrhenius type equation. Besides, empirically derived activation energies of the process have close values both for background (17.3-29.4 kcal/mole) and for enriched soils (25.2 kcal/mole) (see Table 2.4). To parameterize the temperature dependence we choose value 20 kcal/mole ($8.37 \cdot 10^4$ J/mole) for all soil types. On the contrary, we consider pre-exponential factor depending on the soil type: the factor for background soil is five times lower than for soils of the mercury belts, and ten times lower than for the deposits areas. Besides, the emission flux is assumed to be zero for negative values of the soil temperature in the centigrade scale. Fitting total land emission in the Northern Hemisphere to the adopted value we obtain the following temperature dependence of the mercury flux from soil (in $\text{ng/m}^2/\text{h}$):

$$F = \begin{cases} A_s \exp(-E_a / R_{univ} T_s), & T_s > T_0 \\ 0, & T_s \leq T_0 \end{cases}, \quad (2.1)$$

where E_a is the activation energy;

the constant A_s is equal to $3.47 \cdot 10^{14}$ for background soils, $A_s = 1.74 \cdot 10^{15}$ for the mercuriferous belts, and $A_s = 3.47 \cdot 10^{15}$ for deposit areas;

T_s is surface temperature, K;

$T_0 = 273$ K.

Table 2.4. Activation energy of mercury natural emission from background soils

Location	E_a (kcal/mole)	Reference
Tennessee, USA	17.3 - 25.8	<i>Kim et al.</i> , 1995
Tennessee, USA	18.0 - 24.9	<i>Carpí and Linberg</i> , 1998
Quebec, Canada	20.5	<i>Poissant and Casimit</i> , 1998
Michigan, USA	29.4	<i>Zhang et al.</i> , 2001

When describing the emission from sea surfaces we accept the idea by *J. Kim and W. Fitzgerald* [1986], who suggested proportionality of mercury emission from the ocean to primary production of organic carbon in seawater. Monthly mean fields of the ocean primary production [*Behrenfeld and Falkowski, 1997*] available through the Internet [<http://marine.rutgers.edu/opp/>] were used for the parameterization of mercury emission from seawater. The spatial distribution of estimated natural emission of mercury in European region is shown in Fig. 2.1. Rather high emission fluxes are from soils of the geochemical belt in Southern Europe and from coastal seawater with the intensive primary carbon production. The low values of mercury emission over the Mediterranean Sea estimated by this approach are because of low primary productivity in the seawater. These emission fluxes are, probably, underestimated [*Ferrara et al., 2000; Gårdfeldt et al., 2003*], since there are some biotic or abiotic mechanisms of mercury reduction in seawater not described by the parameterization.

During a period of active usage of mercury in human activity more than one million ton was extracted from the lithosphere, and at least half of that came to the atmosphere [*Travnikov and Ryaboshapko, 2002*]. A great amount of mercury was emitted in the process of coal combustion. *W.F.Fitzgerald and R.P.Mason* [1996] believe that 95% of previously emitted mercury has being accumulated in soil over the globe. Enhanced content of mercury in soils should inevitably lead to its re-emission to the atmosphere.

A tentative approach to assess mercury re-emission from European soils was applied basing on conjunction of the MSCE-HM model with a simple box model [*Ryaboshapko and Ilyin, 2001*]. The transport model calculated mercury depositions accumulated during last century. The box model considered European soils as a single reservoir with two output fluxes – re-emission and hydrological leaching. Mercury lifetime in the box according to re-emission was assumed to be 400 year, and according to the leaching – 950 year. Under accepted assumptions the model predicted that by the end of 20th century total re-emission in Europe could make up 50 t/y. The distribution of mercury re-emission from soil in Europe is illustrated in Fig. 2.2. The most significant re-emission fluxes are in Central Europe in the regions where intensive depositions have been observed for a long time. In some heavy polluted areas (Eastern Germany, for example) the re-emission nowadays can exceed the current direct anthropogenic emission.

More sophisticated parameterization of mercury natural emission and re-emission processes requires further research of mercury behavior in soils and seawater.

Fig. 2.1. Spatial distribution of mercury natural emission in Europe

Fig. 2.2. Spatial distribution of mercury re-emission from soils in Europe

Lead and cadmium

Lead and cadmium enter the atmosphere not only because of anthropogenic activity, but also due to natural processes. The volcanic activity, sea salt emission, wind re-suspension, wild forest fires and biogenic emissions are suggested as the main processes responsible for natural emission of these metals [Nriagu, 1989]. According to J. Nriagu [1989], globally averaged flux of lead and cadmium from sea surface is 4 and 0.2 g/km²/y, whereas from land – 54 and 3.7 g/km²/y, respectively. If natural emissions were uniformly distributed over the globe, these fluxes would mean natural emissions within EMEP as much as 900 t/y of lead and 50 t/y of cadmium. These values are much lower than anthropogenic emissions of these metals. However, the available estimates, possibly, do not take into account the accumulation for a long period of heavy metals in the surface layer of European soils. Besides, measurements of heavy metals in seawater indicate significant enrichment (up to orders of magnitude) of the marine surface microlayer with such metals as lead and cadmium especially in polluted regions [e.g. Weisel *et al.*, 1984]. Therefore, fluxes of natural emission and re-emission of lead and cadmium in Europe can be significantly higher than globally average ones. A tentative parameterization of lead and cadmium natural emission and re-emission is used in the current version of the model. It is based on measured concentrations of these pollutants in background regions (Atlantic, South Africa, Eastern Asia). The natural emission and re-emission fluxes are assumed to be uniformly distributed over the sea and land surfaces, and evaluated to fit the measured background concentrations. The resulting values of the emission flux for lead and cadmium are 160 and 8 g/km²/y from sea surface and 220 and 12 g/km²/y from soils, respectively. It is also assumed zero emission from surfaces covered with snow.

2.3. Land cover

Land cover data is mostly required for evaluation of the dry deposition velocities and assessment of ecosystem-specific depositions. Currently a preliminary land cover dataset developed by the Coordinating Centre for Effects (CCE) is used in the model. The dataset consider 17 landuse/landcover categories listed in Table 2.5 (in the calculations we divide the water surface category into the ocean and inland waters).

Table 2.5. Land cover categories of CCE dataset used in the model

1. Temperate coniferous forest	10. Semi-natural
2. Temperate deciduous forest	11. Mediterranean scrub
3. Mediterranean needleleaf forest	12. Wetlands
4. Mediterranean broadleaf forest	13. Tundra
5. Temperate crops	14. Desert/Barren
6. Mediterranean crops	15. Water
7. Root crops	16. Ice
8. Grasslands	17. Urban
9. Wheat	

The dataset is partly based on the database developed in the framework of EC Programme on Coordination of Information on the Environment (CORINE) [dataservice.eea.eu.int]. The information to this database was contributed by European countries. Since the CORINE Land Cover data do not

cover entire EMEP area, Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI) database was used to fill the gaps [http://www.york.ac.uk/inst/sei/APS/projects.html]. In order to unify the CORINE and SEI inventories ecosystem classification EUNIS (European Nature Information System) was adopted.

Parameterization of dry deposition requires some characteristics of the ground surface depending on a landcover category (roughness length, height of vegetation canopy, displacement heights). These characteristics vary from season to season. Five different seasonal categories are considered in the model in accordance with *M.L. Wesely* [1989]:

1. Midsummer with lush vegetation.
2. Autumn with cropland that has not been harvested.
3. Late autumn after frost, no snow.
4. Winter, snow on ground and subfreezing.
5. Transitional spring with partially green short annuals.

Table 2.6 contains the land cover characteristics for the listed above seasons. Roughness length scales for different surfaces and displacement heights are mostly based on [*Brook et al.*, 1999]. Roughness length for water surfaces is a function of the friction velocity given by Eq. (1.40) in *Chapter 1*. The heights of vegetation canopy are taken similar to those used in [*Simpson et al.*, 2003].

Table 2.6. Characteristics of different landcover categories used in the model

Land cover category	z_{0m} (m)					d (m)					H (m)
	1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	
Temperate coniferous forest	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	0.9	15	15	15	15	15	20
Temperate deciduous forest	1.05	1.05	0.95	0.55	0.75	15	15	7	7	10	20
Mediterranean needleleaf forest	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.8	12	12	12	12	12	15
Mediterranean broadleaf forest	1	1	0.9	0.5	0.7	12	12	6	6	8	15
Temperate crops	0.1	0.1	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.7	0.7	0	0	0.3	1
Mediterranean crops	0.2	0.2	0.04	0.02	0.06	1.5	1.5	0	0	0.5	2
Root crops	0.05	0.05	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.4	0.4	0	0	0.2	0.5
Semi-natural	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.4	0.4	0.2	0	0.2	0.5
Wheat	0.1	0.1	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.7	0.7	0	0	0.3	1
Grasslands	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.4	0.4	0.2	0	0.2	0.5
Mediterranean scrub	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2	2	2	1	1	2	3
Wetland	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.4	0.4	0.2	0	0.2	0.5
Tundra	0.05	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.4	0.4	0.2	0	0.2	0.5
Desert/Barren	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	-	-	-	-	-	-
Water *	$f(u^*)$	$f(u^*)$	$f(u^*)$	$f(u^*)$	$f(u^*)$	-	-	-	-	-	-
Ice	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	-	-	-	-	-	-
Urban	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-

* - function of the friction velocity (see Eq. (1.40))

2.4. Chemical reactants

Atmospheric mercury undergoes chemical transformations both in the gaseous and aqueous phase. Description of the chemical processes involving mercury needs data on spatial and temporal distribution of reactant (ozone, sulfur dioxide, and hydroxyl radical) concentrations in the atmosphere.

Global monthly mean data on O₃ and SO₂ concentration in the atmosphere calculated by the MOZART model were used. The original data with spatial resolution 2.8°×2.8° were interpolated to the EMEP grid. The obtained spatial distribution of mean annual O₃ concentration in the lowest model layer is shown in Fig. 2.3. There is a noticeable gradient of ozone concentration from Northern to Southern Europe. Fig. 2.4 illustrates vertical profiles of ozone concentration in the atmosphere. Each line of the plot demonstrates mean annual ozone concentration averaged along cross-sections shown in Fig. 2.3. According to the figure, ozone concentration increases with altitude in both cases expecting more intensive mercury oxidation by ozone at the upper troposphere.

Fig. 2.3. Spatial distribution of ozone concentration in the ground air of Europe. Lines show cross-sections of the vertical profiles

Fig. 2.4. Vertical profiles of ozone concentration averaged across the model domain

Fig. 2.5 shows spatial distribution of sulfur dioxide concentration in the surface air of Europe. Spatial pattern of surface concentrations of sulphur dioxide is highly correlated with location of anthropogenic emission sources. Relatively high concentrations are observed in central and western regions of Europe. Relatively low concentrations are over the Perinea and Scandinavian Peninsulas. As it is shown in Fig. 2.6 the maximum concentrations near the surface and they decrease rapidly with altitude.

For hydroxyl radical in the atmosphere we used modelled monthly mean concentrations from [Spivakovsky *et al.*, 2000]. The original data were interpolated to the EMEP grid. In order to take into account diurnal cycle of OH radical we assume zero concentration at night and concentrations proportional to the cosine of the solar zenith angle during daytime. Besides, air concentrations of OH were decreased by a factor of 10 in the cloud environment and below clouds to account for reduction of its photochemical activity [Seigneur *et al.*, 2001].

Fig. 2.5. Spatial distribution of SO_2 concentration in the ground air of Europe. Lines show cross-sections of the vertical profiles

Fig. 2.6. Vertical profiles of SO_2 concentration averaged across the model domain

Spatial distribution of mean annual hydroxyl radical concentration in the surface air of Europe is shown in Fig. 2.7. The highest concentrations are characteristics of Southern Europe, where surface concentrations where can exceed 0.07 pptv. Vertical distribution of OH radical is characterized by gradual increase with altitude in Atlantic and local maximum the attitude about 2 km in central Europe (Fig. 2.8).

Fig. 2.7. Spatial distribution of OH radical concentration in the ground air of Europe. Lines show cross-sections of the vertical profiles

Fig. 2.8. Vertical profiles of OH radical concentration averaged across the model domain

The model chemistry also considers oxidation of elemental mercury by chlorine both in gaseous and aqueous phase. To date, the direct production of Cl_2 is very poorly characterized. As it is mentioned in [Keene *et al.*, 1999] sea-salt aerosol is the major source of reactive Cl gases (particularly Cl_2) in the global troposphere. Following C.Seigneur *et al.* [2001] we adopt air concentration of molecular chlorine in the lowest model layer over the ocean to be 100 ppt at night and 10 ppt during daytime and zero concentration over land. Besides, the model description of aqueous-phase mercury reduction via decomposition of sulphite complexes requires data on cloud water pH . In order to obtain monthly mean fields of cloud water pH we carried out kriging interpolation of pH measurements in precipitation collected within the EMEP monitoring network [Hjellbrekke, 2002; <http://www.nilu.no/projects/ccc/emepdata.html>]. Values of cloud water pH over the Atlantic Ocean are set equal to those measured at monitoring site IS02 (Irafoss, Iceland), measurements at site IT01 (Montelibretti, Italy) are taken to characterize the Mediterranean region and Northern Africa.

Chapter 3

SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

The model sensitivity to uncertainty of different input parameters and model processes has been investigated. The aims of the analysis were definition of the most critical elements of the model formulation, assessment of the uncertainties introduced by individual parameters and estimation of the overall model uncertainty. Two heavy metals (lead and mercury) were included into the analysis. Lead exemplifies characteristics of particle-bound heavy metals, whereas mercury is characterized by long-lived gaseous form, chemical transformations and principally differs from other metals. The main model output variables considered in the analysis are heavy metal concentration in the ambient air (TGM for mercury), concentration in precipitation and total deposition flux. To reduce the influence of the boundary effects on the analysis the output variables were analysed within the target area, which is somewhat smaller than the model domain (Fig 3.1). Besides, influence of the Mercury Depletion Events (MDE) on the model results was analysed in the Arctic region only (within the Arctic Circle).

Fig. 3.1. Target areas of the sensitivity analysis

3.1. Meteorological variability

The model sensitivity to the variability of meteorological parameters (wind speed, surface pressure, cloudiness, precipitation etc.) was analyzed as a separate case since these parameters are adjusted by the meteorological pre-processor and cannot be considered independently. To assess the model uncertainty due to the variability of meteorological parameters a multi-year (1990-2002) calculation was performed with the same emissions data, initial and boundary concentrations. The obtained mean annual fields of the output parameters were compared between each other and with the average value. To evaluate the inter-annual variation of the model results distribution of the relative deviation was calculated:

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^{met} = \frac{Y_{ij}^{\max} - Y_{ij}^{\min}}{2\bar{Y}_{ij}} 100\%, \quad (3.1)$$

where Y_{ij} is a mean annual value of one of the model output parameters in a gridcell (i,j);

\bar{Y}_{ij} is the parameter average over the whole calculation period.

Probability distributions of the relative deviation over the target area are presented in Figs. 3.2 and 3.3 for lead and mercury respectively. As seen from the figure the relative deviation of lead output parameters varies from 10% to 60% in different parts of the model domain. The same range of variation characterizes mercury concentration in precipitation and total deposition. However, variability of total gaseous mercury is noticeably lower and does not exceed 20%. To quantify the average uncertainty of the model outputs due to meteorological variability the Mean-Square Relative Error (MSRE) was calculated:

$$\varepsilon^{met} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i,j} (\varepsilon_{ij}^{met})^2}, \quad (3.2)$$

where N is the number of gridcells and summing is performed over all cells of the target area.

Fig. 3.2. Cumulative distribution functions of relative deviation of **Pb** concentration in air (a), in precipitation (b), and total deposition (c) due to the inter-annual variability of meteorological parameters

Fig. 3.3. Cumulative distribution functions of relative deviation of **Hg** concentration in air (a), in precipitation (b), and total deposition (c) due to the inter-annual variability of meteorological parameters

The MSRE the main model output variables is presented in Table 3.1 along with the range of the relative deviation variation corresponding to 90% confidence interval.

Table 3.1. Characteristics of the model output uncertainty due to the variability of meteorological parameters

Output parameter	MSRE, %	Range, %
Lead		
Air concentration	28	12 - 44
Concentration in precipitation	26	15 - 37
Total deposition	29	15 - 41
Mercury		
TGM concentration	7	3 - 11
Concentration in precipitation	28	14 - 42
Total deposition	23	12 - 34

3.2. Model sensitivity to parameters and processes

The model sensitivity to different input parameters and to the model processes formulation was estimated by variation of the parameter or switching off the appropriate process. The obtained mean annual fields of the pollutant concentration in air and in precipitation as well as total deposition flux were compared with the base case. The main model parameters included into the sensitivity analysis are listed in Table 3.2. The table also includes expert estimates of the parameters uncertainty (half interval of the relative error) used in Section 3.3 for evaluation of the model uncertainty due to individual parameters. It should be noted that these estimates have rather qualitative character.

Table 3.2. Parameters and processes considered in the sensitivity analysis

Parameter and processes	Notation	Uncertainty
Lead		
Anthropogenic emissions	E_{ant}	50% *
Natural emissions and re-emission	E_{nat}	90%
Wet deposition coefficient	L_{wet}	75%
Dry deposition velocity	V_d	75%
Boundary concentration	C_{bound}	90%
Eddy diffusion coefficient	K_z	50%
Liquid water content	LWC	50%
Aerosol mass median diameter	MMD	50%
Mercury		
Anthropogenic emissions	E_{ant}	50% *
Speciation of anthropogenic emission **	E_{spec}	40%
Natural emissions and re-emission	E_{nat}	90%
Wet deposition coefficient	L_{wet}	75%
Dry deposition velocity (all species)	V_d	75%
Dry deposition of GEM	$V_d (GEM)$	90%
Dry deposition of fog	$V_d (fog)$	90%
Lateral boundary concentration of GEM	$C_{bound} (GEM)$	20%
Lateral boundary concentration of TPM	$C_{bound} (TPM)$	90%
Upper boundary concentration	C_{upp}	50%
Oxidation by O_3 in gas phase	$k_{O_3(gas)}$	50%
Oxidation by O_3 in aqueous phase	$k_{O_3(aq)}$	50%
Oxidation by OH in gas phase	$k_{OH(gas)}$	75%
Oxidation by OH in aqueous phase	$k_{OH(aq)}$	75%
Oxidation by Cl_2 in gas phase	$k_{Cl_2(gas)}$	90%
Oxidation by Cl_2 in aqueous phase	$k_{Cl_2(aq)}$	90%
Reduction through sulphite complexes	$k_{red(ag)}$	50%
Hg ion-chloride equilibrium constant	$K_{Hg^{2+}}$	50%
Solution-adsorption equilibrium constant	K_{sorb}	50%
pH of cloud water	pH	20%
Chloride ion concentration	$[Cl^-]$	90%
Aerosol solubility	K_{part}	50%
Liquid water content	LWC	50%
Henry's constant for Hg^0	H_{Hg^0}	20%
Henry's constant for $HgCl_2$	H_{HgCl_2}	75%

* - only stochastic component of anthropogenic emissions uncertainty is considered. The systematic component (underestimation) is behind the scope of the current research.

** - fraction of oxidized Hg forms (TPM and RGM) in anthropogenic emissions

The change of a model output variable is quantified in each gridcell of the target area by the relative deviation:

$$\varepsilon_{ij}^Y = \frac{Y_{ij} - Y_{ij}^{base}}{Y_{ij}^{base}} \quad (3.3)$$

An example of the model response to variation one of the input parameters is shown in Fig. 3.5. The figure illustrates probability distribution of the relative deviation of the model outputs due to twofold increasing and decreasing of the dry deposition velocity of lead. As seen the most significant effect is on air concentration, which changes can reach 50%. On the contrary, variation of total deposition flux is weaker because of the opposite effects of wet and dry deposition contributions.

To characterize sensitivity of the model output variable Y to variation of input parameter X the sensitivity coefficient is calculated as follows

$$\frac{\delta Y}{\delta X} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i,j} (\varepsilon_{ij}^Y)^2}}{X / X_{base} - 1} \quad (3.4)$$

The presented below analysis of the model sensitivity does not include consideration of separate meteorological parameters by reasons discussed above. Instead, the contribution of these parameters to the model uncertainty is considered in aggregate in Section 1.3.

Lead

The sensitivity coefficients of the main model outputs to uncertainty of input parameters are illustrated for lead in Fig. 3.6. The error bars in the figure show the 90% confidence interval of the sensitivity coefficient variation over the target area. As seen from the figure the model is the most sensitive to anthropogenic, natural emissions along with re-emission (at current calculations natural emission and re-emission make up roughly a half of anthropogenic ones). Among other important parameters are the wet deposition coefficient and the dry deposition velocity, which in its turn is influenced by the aerosol mass median diameter. On the other hand, the model is only weakly sensitive to such parameters as boundary concentrations and the liquid water content.

Fig. 3.5. Cumulative distribution functions of the relative deviation of Pb concentration in air (a), in precipitation (b), and total deposition (c) due to variation of the dry deposition velocity. The curves correspond to twofold increasing and decreasing of the parameter

Fig. 3.6. Coefficients of the model sensitivity to the main input parameters for Pb concentration in air (a), in precipitation (b) and for total Pb deposition flux (c). The error bars show 90% confidence interval

Mercury

The character of the mercury model sensitivity is principally different from that described above. The main reason for that is long residence time of the bulk mercury form in the atmosphere – gaseous elemental mercury (GEM) – and chemical transformations in gaseous and aqueous phases governing mercury removal from the atmosphere. The mercury model sensitivity coefficients to uncertainty of the main input parameters are shown in Fig. 3.7.

Fig. 3.7. Coefficients of the model sensitivity to the main input parameters for TGM concentration (a), Hg concentration in precipitation (b) and for total Hg deposition flux (c). The error bars show 90% confidence interval

The sensitivity of TGM concentration is dominated by boundary concentration of GEM. The contribution of GEM in total gaseous mercury makes up to 99%. Taking into account very long residence time of GEM in the free troposphere (an order of year) it is obvious that this bulk mercury form can easily reach the centre of Europe or even cross the model domain. Sensitivity of TGM concentration to other parameters is significantly lower. The GEM concentration is the most important parameter for Hg concentration in precipitation and total deposition flux as well. However, since these output variables are mostly defined by oxidized mercury forms, they are also quite sensitive to other parameters responsible for emissions, oxidation and removal processes. Among them are anthropogenic emissions and their speciation characteristics, oxidation by ozone in gaseous phase, wet deposition coefficient etc. Besides, as seen a very important parameter is *pH* of cloud water. It should be noted that at the base values of the model parameters the sulphite channel of Hg reduction in aqueous phase is practically inactive due to suppressing reaction with chloride ion available in excess leading to formation of stable chloride complexes. But situation changes considerably if *pH* increased because of activation of the reduction channel. It leads to significant decrease of Hg concentration in precipitation. Another specific feature of mercury removal is very low sensitivity to natural emission along with re-emission within the model domain. It is expected that mercury is emitted from natural sources as well as re-emitted in elemental form. As a result the most part of these emissions flow out the model domain not being oxidized and removed.

3.3. Uncertainty due to individual parameters

Uncertainty of different input parameters can differ significantly. Therefore contribution of an input parameter to the overall model uncertainty depends not only on the model sensitivity but also on inaccuracy of the parameter itself. To evaluate the uncertainty of a model output *Y* due to contribution of an input parameter *X* we multiplies the appropriate sensitivity coefficient by the uncertainty of the parameter ε_X :

$$E_X^Y = \frac{\delta Y}{\delta X} \varepsilon_X . \quad (3.5)$$

Estimates of the input parameters uncertainties are presented in Table 3.2. The aggregate contribution of meteorological parameters is based on the results presented in Section 3.1. It should be noted that the following analysis results to significant extent depend on the uncertainties of input parameters and should be considered as tentative because of rough character of the input uncertainties estimates.

Lead

Uncertainties of the main output variables for lead caused by inaccuracies of input parameters are illustrated in Fig. 3.8. The most significant uncertainties are introduced by anthropogenic and natural emissions along with re-emission and exceed 30% on average. High uncertainty of natural emission and re-emission leads to their contribution to the overall uncertainty at least comparable with the anthropogenic one. Meteorological parameters and characteristics of removal processes also cause considerable model uncertainty.

Fig. 3.8. Uncertainty of Pb concentration in air (a), in precipitation (b) and of total Pb deposition flux (c) due to inaccuracy of main input parameters. The error bars show 90% confidence interval

Mercury

The most important parameters determined uncertainties of mercury concentration in air, in precipitation as well as total deposition flux are ranged in Fig. 3.9. The highest uncertainty of TGM concentration is due to the boundary concentration of GEM and do not exceed 20%. On the other hand, this parameter is not so important for two other output variables. The uncertainty of Hg concentration in precipitation is mostly determined by uncertainty of meteorological parameters, removal characteristics and oxidation by ozone in gas phase. Besides, anthropogenic emissions and boundary conditions for TPM are also important. Meteorological variability and anthropogenic emission along with its speciation introduced the most significant uncertainty to total Hg deposition flux.

Fig. 3.9. Uncertainty of TGM concentration (a), Hg concentration in precipitation (b) and of total Hg deposition flux (c) due to inaccuracy of main input parameters. The error bars show 90% confidence interval

MDE

The effect of Mercury Depletion Events on total annual Hg deposition in the Arctic was investigated using the tentative parameterization of the phenomenon (see Section 1.3). Fig. 3.10 shows probability distribution of the relative deviation of total annual Hg deposition due to effect of MDE within the Arctic Circle. In some areas of the Arctic total annual deposition of mercury can increase up to 100% and more. As seen from the spatial distribution of the relative deviation (Fig. 3.11) the most significant increase takes place over the coastal areas of the Arctic Ocean. It could be concluded that this short-term phenomenon (occurring during several weeks in the springtime) can have significant effect on the long-term pollution of the Arctic with mercury. However, further research of MDE kinetics is required to develop reliable parameterization of the phenomenon for the model.

Fig. 3.10. Cumulative distribution function of the relative deviation of total annual Hg deposition due to effect of MDE

Fig. 3.11. Spatial distribution of the relative deviation of total annual Hg deposition due to effect of MDE. Solid line depicts the Arctic Circle

3.4. Overall uncertainty

The overall model uncertainty can be roughly estimated from the uncertainties due to individual parameters using the following equation

$$E^Y = \sqrt{\sum_X (E_X^Y)^2}. \quad (3.6)$$

Estimated uncertainties of the main model parameters for lead and mercury are presented in Table 3.3. As it was mentioned above results of this analysis to significant extent depend on the uncertainties of input parameters and should be considered as tentative.

The intrinsic model uncertainty includes contributions of all model parameters except anthropogenic, natural emissions and re-emission. The overall model uncertainty along with other parameters includes uncertainty due to anthropogenic, natural emissions and re-emission. However, only the stochastic component of anthropogenic emissions uncertainty is considered. A possible influence of the systematic error (underestimation) is not included. The range indicates 90% confidence interval of the uncertainty variation over the model domain. The intrinsic model uncertainty of lead concentration in air, concentration in precipitation and total deposition varies from 20% to 65% over the domain with average values 43%, 40% and 33% respectively. The overall uncertainties reach 60% on average

(the range 30-97%). The intrinsic model uncertainty of mercury differs for different outputs. It does not exceed 20% on average for TGM concentration (the range 16-22%) but reaches 40% for total deposition and 50% for concentration in precipitation (the ranges 20-57% and 29-74% respectively). The overall uncertainty for mercury only slightly exceeds the intrinsic one indicating limited effect of emissions uncertainty on the model results.

Table 3.3. Model intrinsic and the overall uncertainties of the main model output parameters

Output parameter	Intrinsic		Overall *	
	Uncertainty, %	Range, %	Uncertainty, %	Range, %
Lead				
Air concentration	43	22 - 64	65	39 - 97
Concentration in precipitation	40	20 - 57	61	32 - 85
Total deposition	33	19 - 49	58	31 - 81
Mercury				
TGM concentration	19	16 - 22	20	16 - 23
Concentration in precipitation	53	29 - 74	56	29 - 80
Total deposition	39	20 - 57	46	20 - 70

* - only stochastic component of anthropogenic emissions uncertainty is considered. The systematic component (underestimation) is not included

3.5. Conclusions of the sensitivity analysis

The main conclusions of the sensitivity analysis are:

- Uncertainty of modelling results due to inter-annual variability of meteorological parameters amounts to 20-30% on average except that of TGM concentration, which does not exceed 10%.
- The model outputs for lead are the most sensitive to anthropogenic emissions, natural emission and re-emission and to removal parameters. Sensitivity of the mercury model outputs is highest to boundary concentration of gaseous elemental mercury and to lower extent to anthropogenic emissions (along with speciation), cloud water *pH* and wet deposition characteristics as well as to oxidation by ozone in gaseous phase.
- Total annual deposition of mercury over the coastal areas of the Arctic Ocean can increase by 100% and more due to the effect of Mercury Depletion Events.
- The most significant contribution to the model uncertainty for lead is made by emissions, meteorological parameters and removal characteristics. Beside these parameters, the mercury model uncertainty is also determined by boundary concentration of gaseous elemental mercury (it is dominating for TGM concentration) and oxidation by ozone in gaseous phase.
- The intrinsic model uncertainty of lead concentration in air, concentration in precipitation and total deposition are estimated as 43%, 40% and 33% respectively; the appropriate uncertainties for mercury are 19%, 53% and 39%. The overall uncertainty of these main model outputs can be assessed as 65%, 61%, 58% respectively for lead and 20%, 56%, 46% for mercury. However, it should be noted that the final values of the uncertainty to significant extent depend on estimates of inaccuracy of input parameters.

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Annex A**ADVECTION TESTS**

Performance of the model advection scheme was examined in the classical numerical tests: rotational flow (called also as 'solid body rotation') and strong deformational flow [Smolarkiewicz, 1982]. The standard version of the model was applied in the tests. For this purpose the appropriate artificial wind field was used for the calculations and all emissions were switched off. Since both tests simulate non-divergent flow the surface pressure was set to a constant. Besides, the model orography was flattened. The initial distribution of a substance mixing ratio had a shape of three-dimensional ellipsoid with the circular cross section in the horizontal. The centre of the distribution was located at the fourth model layer. The substance mixing ratio is decreased linearly from the ellipsoid centre to some background value at its boundaries. An important issue of the tests is non-zero background mixing ratio, which allows testing the scheme positive definiteness and monotonicity. The three-dimensional advection was modelled under the defined conditions for a certain time interval and the resulting distribution was analysed. The main difference of the tests performed from the original ones is the model operation under the real conditions of the polar stereographic projection instead of flat Cartesian geometry. The wind fields were first defined on the Earth's surface and then used for advection modelling on the projection. Besides, three-dimensional character of the advection leads to more significant artificial diffusion in comparison with original two-dimensional tests of the scheme [Bott, 1992].

Rotational flow

The objective of the rotational flow test is to examine the model ability to simulate a pollutant horizontal advective transport and to evaluate artificial diffusion of the numerical scheme. The wind field of the rotational flow is illustrated in Fig. A.1 by circular isolines of large radius. The axis of the rotational flow is located at the zero meridian and sloped down from the Earth axis with the angle 30° . The center of the initial distribution with the radius of 5 gridcells is located at the cell (25,25). Since the flow is non-divergent the uniform distribution should remain uniform, whereas the ellipsoid should theoretically be transported unchangeable. However, in reality it is smoothed down due to the artificial diffusion.

Results of the test are presented in Fig. A.1. The numbered sets of smaller concentric circles show the cone location and shape at different moments of its rotation. Fig. A.2 show the results in the form of the three-dimensional surface of mixing ratio distribution. As seen from the figures the initial distribution somewhat changes its shape due to the numerical dispersion and is smoothed down because of the artificial diffusion. The smoothing of the initial distribution after the whole rotation does not exceed 30% that is reasonable taking into account small radius of the initial distribution. Besides, insignificant non-monotonicity appeared by the end of the rotation. Thus, the advection scheme does not produce considerable distortions, has comparatively low artificial diffusion and almost monotone.

Fig. A.1. Initial conditions and the results of the rotational flow test. Concentric circles of large radius denote wind velocity isolines. Smaller circles are the mixing ratio distribution isolines at the fourth model layer: 1 – initial; 2 – after 96 iterations; 3 – 192 iterations; 4 – 288 iterations; 5 – 384 iterations; 6 – 480 iterations; 7 – 576 iterations

Fig. A.2. The same as in Fig. A.1 but in the form of a three-dimensional surface of mixing ratio distribution

Deformational flow

The objective of the deformational flow test is to examine the model stability in strong deformational flows and evaluate possible time-splitting error [Bott, 1993; Easter, 1993]. The velocity field for the deformational flow test and the initial mixing ratio distribution are presented in Fig. A.3. Zonal and meridional components of the wind are determined by the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned} V_{\lambda} &= 4 \sin(10\lambda) \sin(16\varphi), \\ V_{\varphi} \cos \varphi &= 2.5 \cos(10\lambda) \cos(16\varphi), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where λ and φ are longitude and latitude of a gridcell, respectively.

The center of the initial distribution with the radius of 16 gridcells is located at the cell (64,63). As it is seen from the figure the wind field is built up from sets of symmetrical vortices. Since the flow is non-divergent again a uniform distribution should remain uniform except gridcells where mass from the initial ellipsoidal distribution incoming. But anyway mixing ratio values should remain limited at any point of the domain.

Fig. A.3. Initial conditions of the deformational flow test. Cell-shaped curves denote wind velocity isolines. Circles show the initial mixing ratio distribution isolines at the fourth model layer

Results of the experiment are presented in Fig. A.4. The figures illustrate transformation of the initial distribution in the deformation flow and correspond to different time moments (or different numbers of iterations). As one can see the mass is coming along the boundaries of the vortices and is penetrating to the neighboring ones. The difference of this deformational flow test from the original one [Smolarkiewicz, 1982] is that boundaries of the vortices do not exactly coincide with gridcell borders. It leads to mass exchange between the vortices and smearing of the initial distribution over the domain. The maximum value of the distribution decreases in time until two stable elevations are formed. That means that the model is stable to the deformational flow and no observable time-splitting error appears.

Fig. A.4. Results of the deformational flow test. Three-dimensional surface of mixing ratio distribution at the fourth model layer: a – initial; b – after 48 iterations; c – 96 iterations; d – 192 iterations; e – 384 iterations; f – 1536 iterations

Annex B

CALCULATION OF THE VERTICAL VELOCITY

A possible approach to adjust the input meteorological fields to the model discretization is derivation of vertical wind velocity σ from the continuity equation for air at each time step [Odman and Russel, 2000]. For the exact mass conservation it is important to apply the same numerical scheme used for description of species advection to solution of the continuity equation. The solution is performed in two steps:

Step 1. Solution of the horizontal constituent of the air continuity equation for p^* using Bott advection scheme:

$$\frac{\partial p^*}{\partial t} = -m^2 \nabla_H \cdot \left(p^* \frac{V_H}{m} \right) \quad (\text{B.1})$$

For the initial condition the surface pressure at the beginning of the time step $(p^*)_t$ is used. As a result a three-dimensional distribution of the intermediate pressure $(p^*)_{t+\Delta t/2} = f(x, y, \sigma)$ is obtained.

Step 2. Solution of the vertical constituent of the air continuity equation for the vertical velocity σ :

$$\frac{\partial p^*}{\partial t} = -\frac{\Gamma \partial}{\Gamma \partial} (p^* \sigma) \quad (\text{B.2})$$

The intermediate pressure $(p^*)_{t+\Delta t/2}$ from the Step 1 is used as the initial condition; and the surface pressure at the end of the time step $(p^*)_{t+\Delta t} = f(x, y)$ interpolated from the input data is considered as a final condition. Keeping notations from [Bott, 1989a] the surface pressure at the end of the time step can be express as follows for each layer k of the model domain

$$(p^*)_{t+\Delta t} = (p^*)_{t+\Delta t/2} - I_k^{up} - I_k^{down} + \frac{\Delta \sigma_{k-1}}{\Delta \sigma_k} I_{k-1}^{up} + \frac{\Delta \sigma_{k+1}}{\Delta \sigma_k} I_{k+1}^{down}, \quad k = 1, K_{max}, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where the integrals of mass coming up and down through the upper and lower borders of the gridcell, respectively, are given by :

$$I_k^{up} = \int_{-1/2}^{-1/2+\alpha_k^{up}} p^*(\xi) d\xi, \quad I_k^{down} = \int_{1/2-\alpha_k^{down}}^{1/2} p^*(\xi) d\xi, \quad (\text{B.4})$$

pressure distribution in a gridcell is approximated by the 2nd order polynomial:

$$p^*(\xi) = \sum_{n=0}^2 a_{k,n} \xi^n, \quad \xi = \frac{\sigma - \sigma_k}{\Delta \sigma_k} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

and the local Courant numbers are calculated as follows:

$$\alpha_k^{up} = \frac{|\sigma_k^{up}| \Delta t}{\Delta \sigma_k}, \quad \alpha_k^{down} = \frac{|\sigma_k^{down}| \Delta t}{\Delta \sigma_k} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

The integrals of mass coming through the gridcell borders are derived from Eq. (B.3):

$$\begin{cases} I_k^{up} = (\rho_k^*)_{t+\Delta t/2} - (\rho^*)_{t+\Delta t} - I_k^{down} + \frac{\Delta\sigma_{k-1}}{\Delta\sigma_k} I_{k-1}^{up}, & I_k^{up} > 0 \\ I_{k+1}^{down} = \frac{\Delta\sigma_k}{\Delta\sigma_{k+1}} \left((\rho^*)_{t+\Delta t} - (\rho_k^*)_{t+\Delta t/2} + I_k^{down} - \frac{\Delta\sigma_{k-1}}{\Delta\sigma_k} I_{k-1}^{up} \right), & I_k^{up} \leq 0 \end{cases}, \quad k = 1, K_{max}. \quad (B.7)$$

The calculation is started from the lowest layer where the mass flux through the ground surface is absent: $I_0^{up} = 0$ and $I_1^{down} = 0$. Substituting the polynomial approximation (B.5) to the Eqs. (B.4) and equating the obtained expressions to the values of the mass integrals calculated in Eq. (B.7) one can derive linear algebraic equations for the local Courant numbers α_k^{up} or α_k^{down} at borders of each gridcell ($k = 1, K_{max}$):

$$\sum_{n=0}^2 \frac{a_{k,n}}{(n+1)2^{n+1}} (-1)^n \left[1 - (1 - 2\alpha_k^{up})^{n+1} \right] = I_k^{up} \quad (B.8)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^2 \frac{a_{k+1,n}}{(n+1)2^{n+1}} \left[1 - (1 - 2\alpha_{k+1}^{down})^{n+1} \right] = I_{k+1}^{down} \quad (B.9)$$

Only one of Eqs. (B.8) and (B.9) is taken for each gridcell border. For example, for the upper border of gridcell k Eq. (B.8) is chosen if $I_k^{up} > 0$ and Eq. (B.9) in the opposite case. The Eqs. (B.8) or (B.9) are solved for α_k^{up} or α_k^{down} , respectively, using the Newton's method. Vertical velocities are derived from the appropriate Courant numbers using expressions (B.6).

Annex C

HEMISPHERIC MODEL OF HEAVY METAL POLLUTION (MSCE-HM-Hem)

The hemispheric MSCE-HM-Hem model has been developed in MSC-East to meet the tasks of the Convention on Long-Range Transboundary Air Pollution on the assessment of the atmospheric transport and depositions of heavy metal in the Northern Hemisphere, evaluation of the intercontinental transport and support of the regional pollution modelling with the boundary conditions. The model considers mercury emissions from anthropogenic and natural sources, transport in the atmosphere, chemical transformations both in gaseous and aqueous phases, and deposition to the ground.

The model computation domain covers the whole Northern Hemisphere with spatial resolution 2.5° both in zonal and meridional directions. The surface grid structure of the model domain is shown in Fig. C.1. To avoid a singularity at the pole point, peculiar to the spherical coordinates, the grid has a special circular mesh of radius 1.25° including the North Pole. In the vertical direction the model domain consists of eight irregular levels of terrain-following sigma-pressure (σ) coordinate defined as a ratio of local atmospheric pressure to the ground surface pressure. The vertical grid structure of the model is presented in Fig. C.2.

Fig. C.1. Horizontal grid structure of the model domain. The model grid with resolution $2.5^\circ \times 2.5^\circ$ and the pole grid cell

Fig. C.2. Vertical grid structure of the model domain. Eight terrain-following σ -levels: 1 – = 0.99; 2 – 0.96; 3 – 0.91; 4 – 0.85; 5 – 0.77; 6 – 0.68; 7 – 0.55; 8 – 0.4

The model description of mercury atmospheric transport is based on the three-dimensional advection-diffusion equation adapted to the (σ) coordinate [Jacobson, 1999]:

$$\frac{\partial (qp_s)}{\partial t} = -\nabla_H \cdot (qp_s \mathbf{V}_H) - \frac{\partial (qp_s \sigma)}{\partial \sigma} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \sigma} \left[K_z \frac{g^2 \rho^2}{p_s^2} \frac{\partial (qp_s)}{\partial \sigma} \right] + \sum_i S_i \quad (\text{C.1})$$

Here q is the pollutant mixing ratio; $\dot{\sigma}$ is the vertical scalar velocity in the (σ, p) coordinate; ∇_H and \mathbf{V}_H denote horizontal divergence operator and horizontal wind velocity respectively; K_z is the vertical eddy diffusion coefficient; and g is the gravitational acceleration. In Eq. (C.1) we omitted horizontal components of eddy diffusion because of the coarse horizontal grid resolution. The atmospheric advection is solved using the Bott scheme modified for the spherical co-ordinates. An implicit treatment of the vertical eddy diffusion is chosen in order to avoid restrictions on the integration time step because of possible sharp gradients of the pollutant mixing ratio.

Parameterizations of the removal processes and chemical transformations of mercury are the same as for the regional model (MSCE-HM) described above.

The model is driven by off-line meteorological parameters supplied by the low atmosphere diagnostics system (SDA) developed in co-operation with Hydro-meteorological Centre of Russia. The system provides 6-hour weather prediction data along with estimates of the atmospheric boundary layer parameters and covers the Northern Hemisphere with the model spatial resolution. NCEP/DOE re-analysis data is utilized as the input information for the system.

Anthropogenic emission of mercury in the Northern Hemisphere was evaluated basing on the global emission inventory for 1995 published by *J.Pacyna et al.* (2003). According to these data, anthropogenic emission of mercury in the Northern Hemisphere is about 1900 t/y. Spatial distribution of anthropogenic mercury emissions in the Northern Hemisphere is shown in Fig. C.3. As seen from the figure the most significant emission sources are located in South-Eastern Asia, Europe and eastern part of North America. Available data on the natural emission of mercury are rather uncertain. To take into account natural emission of mercury we used global estimates by *Lamborg et al.* (2002). Spatial distribution of natural emission fluxes (including re-emission) was obtained by scattering the total value throughout the globe depending on mercury content in soils and the surface temperature. The total natural emission and re-emission of mercury in the Northern Hemisphere is estimated as much as 1600 t/y.

Fig. C.3. Spatial distribution of anthropogenic mercury emissions in the Northern Hemisphere in 1995

A uniform distribution of elemental mercury concentration is set at the upper boundary – 0.185 pptv (corresponding to about 1.5 ng/m³ at 1 atm and 20°C). To take into account the inter-hemispheric transport of mercury a fixed gradient of elemental mercury concentration of 0.05 ng/m³/degree is set at the equator. One-year model spin-up is performed to fill up the atmosphere with mercury.

Modeling results show that elevated mercury concentrations in the ambient air are characteristics of regions with high emissions such as Europe, South-eastern Asia and eastern part of North America. Figure C.4 shows total gaseous mercury concentration profiles coming along meridians through two the most contaminated and one background region. As one can see from the figure even in the remote parts of the Pacific Ocean, as well as in the Arctic, mercury concentration in the ambient air does not fall below 1.5 ng/m³.

Spatial distribution of total annual mercury deposition (wet and dry) in the Northern Hemisphere is illustrated in Fig. C.5. High deposition fluxes were obtained for contaminated regions but also for some background regions characterized by large precipitation amount (North Atlantic and Pacific). This can be explained by wide dispersion of atmospheric mercury over the globe and prevailing role of wet scavenging in mercury removal from the atmosphere.

Fig. C.4. Profiles of total gaseous mercury concentration in the ambient air of the Northern Hemisphere

Fig. C.5. Spatial distribution of total annual mercury deposition (wet and dry) in the Northern Hemisphere

Comparison of modelled and measured values of mercury wet deposition is presented in Fig. C.6. Measurements from European (EMEP network) and North American (NADP/MDN network) monitoring sites was used in the comparison (Fig. C.7). As seen the mean ratio between measured and calculated values is close to unity; the maximum difference between them does not exceed a factor of two.

Fig. C.6. Calculated versus measured values of annual wet deposition of mercury. Dashed line shows the two-fold difference

Fig. C.7. Monitoring sites used in the model validation

Detailed description of the hemispheric model is published in [Travnikov and Ryaboshapko, 2002].